

Co-UDlabs

Building Collaborative Urban Drainage
research Labs communities

D4.4. Final report on the project exploitation initiatives and related impacts on innovation, including dissemination and communication activities

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Background: about the Co-UDlabs Project

Co-UDlabs is an EU-funded project aiming to integrate research and innovation activities in the field of Urban Drainage Systems (UDS) to address pressing public health, flood risks and environmental challenges.

Bringing together 17 unique research facilities, Co-UDlabs offers training and free access to a wide range of high-level scientific instruments, smart monitoring technologies and digital water analysis tools for advancing knowledge and innovation in Urban drainage systems.

Co-UDlabs aims to create a urban drainage large-scale facilities network to provide opportunities for monitoring water quality, UDS performance and smart and open data approaches.

The main objective of the project is to provide a transnational multidisciplinary collaborative research infrastructure that will allow stakeholders, academic researchers, and innovators in the urban drainage water sector to come together, share ideas, co-produce project concepts and then benefit from access to top-class research infrastructures to develop, improve and demonstrate those concepts, thereby building a collaborative European Urban Drainage innovation community.

The initiative will facilitate the uptake of innovation in traditional buried pipe systems and newer green-blue infrastructure, with a focus on increasing the understanding of asset deterioration and improving system resilience.

List of acronyms

Acronym / Abbreviation	Meaning / Full text
CA	Consortium Agreement
GA	Grant Agreement
IAB	Innovation Advisory Board
IP	Intellectual Property
JRA	Joint Research Activity
KER	Key Exploitable Result
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
PEDR	Plan for Exploitation and dissemination of Results
RI	Research Infrastructure
TA	Transnational Access
UDS	Urban Drainage System
WP	Work Package

Executive summary

This document is a deliverable of the Co-UDlabs project, funded under the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101008626.

Deliverable 4.4 is the final report of all communication, dissemination and exploitation activities that have been achieved since the beginning of the project (Month 1) and until Month 48, as part of Work Package (WP) 4 and in alignment with the Plan for Dissemination and Exploitation of Results (PEDR).

This report provides a detailed and exhaustive list of all communication and dissemination activities performed since the beginning of the project in the framework of WP4 to ensure the maximum, long-lasting impact of Co-UDlabs. It includes also the evaluation of the Key Performance Indicators set for these actions, and a description of the work performed under the exploitation task, including the identification of a list of Key Exploitable Results (KERs) and their related exploitation strategies.

In summary, the project has reached a very satisfactory level of visibility among a variety of stakeholders of the urban drainage sector: researchers, industrials, students, policymakers, citizens. The communication and dissemination activities during the project lifetime have been really satisfying, overstepping in some cases the project expectations, as demonstrated by the KPIs identified and monitored by the project (see Annex 4 for details).

Project partners have been very active, in particular in the final months of the project, dedicating their efforts in organizing the final trainings of the project and the final Infoday, and in preparing several dissemination materials, such as scientific publications, deliverables, a final media press kit, a final press release and a series of policy briefs. All project partners have been actively involved in the dissemination of the project results by providing content and promoting the project through their website and contact networks.

In addition, partners are currently planning their participation in some upcoming events which will take place after the end of the project to disseminate project’s results from both the JRA and transnational access activities, demonstrating the willingness of partners in keep on collaborating and building on the results of Co-UDlabs in the future.

1. Dissemination and Communication Strategy

Co-UDlabs integrated along the project many activities to enhance the dissemination and exploitation strategy, maximize the expected impact and boost the project sustainability and project legacy after the EU-funding. The considerable geographic coverage of the project provides a strong foundation for a much broader engagement, and ultimately for the basis upon which to work towards long term sustainability for the UDS community. In the framework of the dissemination and communication strategy, we pursued:

- **Dissemination for Awareness:** to ensure the project is known to relevant stakeholders in the field of urban drainage, municipalities and public authorities’ planners, and the public in general.
- **Dissemination for Understanding:** to encourage a better understanding of the project results leading to greater engagement of external stakeholders and a better future uptake of the project outcomes. To do so, we not only disseminated project results but also success stories related to the technological development within the project and the use of RIs by external groups in the framework of the Transnational access.
- **Dissemination for Action:** to make the scientific community, stakeholders and decision makers aware of the potential uses of the technologies developed in the project, to ensure adoption of technologies, processes and services being developed by the project partners, to enhance participation of relevant actors to our training events.

1.1. Dissemination and communication activities

The communication activities that are part of the dissemination plan of the project were tailored to ensure that important messages were widespread to the adequate targeted audience and that the public at large got connected with Co-UDlabs RI. Such activities complemented the dissemination as they “translated” the sometimes-complex results into easy-to-understand resources focusing more on the impacts and added value for the end-users of Co-UDlabs and the society in general.

The main objectives of the communication and dissemination activities of the project were:

- To show how European collaboration has achieved more than would have otherwise been possible, notably in achieving scientific excellence, contributing to competitiveness, and solving societal challenges.
- To show how the outcomes are relevant to people’s everyday lives, by creating jobs, introducing novel technologies, or enhancing the quality of life of EU citizens and better protecting the environment, making people’s lives more comfortable in other ways.
- To better use of the results, by making sure they are taken up by decision-makers to influence policy-making and by industry and the scientific community to ensure a follow-up of the development of technology.

The different dissemination and communication activities, as well as the tools created and implemented during the project lifetime, are presented below.

1.1.1. Visual identity

The project branding was developed at the start of the project to help all partners to communicate about it in a uniform, consistent, and professional manner. It includes the project logo, project identity and style guide, templates for Word and PowerPoint documents.

The pictograph of the **logo** is a stylistic representation of a urban background (three buildings) and an element representing the green infrastructures (a leaf). The logo is being used in all communication materials, with or without the baseline “Collaborative Urban Drainage Research Lab Communities”. The project’s graphical identity includes fonts, colors and texts directly derived from the project logotype. Such visual identity is defined by the project logo and is being used in all dissemination tools and printed materials.

Templates for the project deliverables, meeting agenda and minutes have also been produced during the first months of the project, together with a PowerPoint template used by the partners to present Co-UDlabs both in internal and external events.

Figure 1. Co-UDlabs templates: PowerPoint presentation, deliverable, agenda and minutes

1.1.2. Communication materials

The following communication materials have been prepared by Euronovia and distributed to the project partners to ensure effective communication and increase public awareness of the project.

1.1.2.1. Flyer, brochure and factsheet

A project **flyer** with general information on the project and the research infrastructures available in the framework of the transnational access was created in October 2021. The flyer has been distributed to partners who printed it and distributed it when organizing or attending external events. The flyer is available in English, Spanish and French.

Figure 2. Co-UDlabs flyer

A **16-pages brochure** focused on Transnational Access, with information useful to launch the second TA call (July 2023), a description of the RIs available within Co-UDlabs, modalities of access, and a short summary of projects selected during the first TA call, was prepared in May 2023. It was made available online on the Co-UDlabs website and printed for distribution at national and international conferences with the aim of reaching potential users of our research infrastructures (academia, industry, and water operators) and encourage them to apply for the second call for transnational access, which was launched in July 2023 at a Co-UDlabs workshop within the Novatech 2023 conference, taking place in Lyon (France). The brochure was finalised and presented to the consortium for communication use by M24

Figure 3. Brochure on TA access

A **factsheet** focused on the first Co-UDlabs Transnational Access call was published at M25. It features a description of the 13 projects selected during the 1st Co-UDlabs TA campaign, with pictures and testimonials from RI users. The objective of the document was to showcase the type of experiments conducted at the Co-UDlabs RIs in order to attract new users for the second TA call. The factsheet was made available online on the project website and printed for distribution at events.

2 infographics were also created and distributed online to communicate the results of the 2 calls for Transnational Access on the project website and social media.

1.1.2.2. Poster and roll-up banner

A project **poster** and a **roll-up banner** were created in the first months of the project, printed and used during external conferences and events attended by the consortium to promote and present the results arising from the project. The roll-up banner is also available in Spanish and French.

Figure 4. Co-UDlabs poster and roll-up banner

1.1.2.3. Press releases and articles

A **press release** was drafted in July 2021 to summarize the most important information related to the project (scope, objectives, messages) to help the consortium to communicate the right information about the project. This press release was translated into French and Spanish and distributed by the project partners to their contact networks. It is available for download in the project website: https://co-udlabs.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/09/CO-UDLABS_press-release-website.pdf.

Another press release was published by UDC in their website to present the outputs of the final event of the project: udc.es/es/novas/A-Universidade-da-Coruna-presenta-en-Bruxelas-os-resultados-do-proxecto-europeo-Co-UDlabs-sobre-os-sistemas-de-drenaxe-urbana/.

A **final press release** was published at the end of April 2025 to announce the end of the project, its main achievements and its legacy. It was distributed through the project website, social media, newsletter and by partners to their contact networks. It is available for download in the project website: <https://co-udlabs.eu/dissemination/communication-material/>.

2 articles in specialized magazines have been published by project partners:

- In March 2024 by EAWAG in the Horizonte magazine for scientific research in Switzerland: Wo die Abwasser erzählen - Ausgabe 140
- “EU-Laborverbund: Forschung und Innovationskraft für städtische Entwässerungssysteme”, by IKT in the 2021 annual report of the research organisation JRF

In addition, **5 articles** about Co-UDlabs were **published in the newsletter of the IAHR/IWA joint committee on urban drainage (JCUD)** - in May 2021, May 2022, March 2023 (<https://iahr.oss-accelerate.aliyuncs.com/upload/file/20240124/1706067576157206.pdf>), March 2024 (<https://iahr.oss-accelerate.aliyuncs.com/upload/file/20240402/1712023100505828.pdf>) and March 2025 (https://jcup.org/wp-content/uploads/2025/03/2025_jcup_newsletter_final.pdf). An article on the end of Co-UDlabs was also published in the EWA newsletter in February 2025 (EWA Newsletter April - Issue 02/2025).

1.1.2.4. Newsletter

Another essential tool to keep in touch with the stakeholders is the edition of a project newsletter. **7 Co-UDlabs newsletters** have been sent out to subscribers and are also available on the project website and disseminated through social media and the contact networks of the project partners to maximize its dissemination. In addition, **7 additional specific campaigns** were sent out to the newsletter subscribers to promote specific activities (hackathons, Co-UDlabs event at Novatech, launch of the TA calls, UDRAIN, final infoday).

The size of the project mailing increased over the years up to **546 contacts**. The newsletters are available for download at <https://co-udlabs.eu/dissemination/newsletter/>.

Figure 5. Examples of Co-UDlabs newsletters

1.1.2.5. Videos and other communication material

A **motion design video** was created at M20 (December 2022) to present Co-UDlabs objectives, activities and expected impacts in an attractive and dynamic way. The video is available on the Co-UDlabs website as well as in the project **YouTube channel** (<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=KjgBKppROVvk>) which was created at M12 (www.shorturl.at/emp23) to gather all project videos. The channel contains **26 videos**, including the recordings of the project webinars, infoday, Deltares courses, partners' interviews, obtaining more than 1600 views.

Figure 6. Co-UDlabs YouTube channel

In addition, an interview of Elodie Brelot from GRAIE has been recorded and uploaded in the French Actu Environnement YouTube channel (« Le but est de sortir les résultats de recherche des cartons pour améliorer la gestion de l’eau » - YouTube) registering 406 views.

1.1.3. Co-UDlabs website

The project website (<https://www.co-udlabs.eu/>) was of crucial importance to enhance the visibility of Co-UDlabs as it served as the main communication tool for the wide dissemination of the project activities, deliverables, activities and outcomes.

Figure 7. Co-UDlabs website landing page

The website includes information on the project scope, objectives and activities, partners, research infrastructures and information on the dissemination activities and project documents. A specific section of the website is dedicated to the Transnational Access (TA), with useful information on the calls for proposals and related launching events.

Created in October 2021, the Co-UDlabs website has been frequently updated with new content. It will be available online for two more years following the end of the project. The website includes the following sections:

- The **homepage** provides an overview of the project scope and concept and a selection of latest news;
- **About us:** it provides information on the objectives, workplan, expected impacts and the partners involved in the project;
- **Access:** this section includes information on transnational access results, a complete description of the research facilities available within the consortium, as well as on testimonials from RI users;
- **Research:** it includes information on the Joint Research Activities and main tools and outputs produced by the partners in the course of the project;
- **Networking:** a section with information on the different networking activities and trainings offered by the consortium;
- **Dissemination:** provides information on the project communication material, deliverables, publications, events, newsletter and success stories of project activities;
- **News:** a page including the list of news published by the consortium;
- **Events:** it includes information on future and past events organised by the project partners within the project;
- **Contact:** it includes the email address to reach us with specific questions as well as the link to the contact form created on Limesurvey to become part of the project community;
- **Links to social media** (Co-UDlabs LinkedIn and X accounts)

The impact of the website is monitored using Google Analytics. In the period from October 2021 to April 2025, the website was visited by 3 063 unique visitors, with 21 311 page views and an average visit duration of 3:22 minutes.

Figure 8. Overview of the Co-UDlabs website page views over time

The website received excellent worldwide coverage, with visitors spread over all continents (105 countries mapped), demonstrating a worldwide interest in the project. The top 10 countries of origin of the website’s visitors are: Spain, France, UK, Netherlands, Germany, Netherlands, Colombia, Switzerland, Denmark, Italy and Belgium, followed by Canada and United States.

Figure 9. Co-UDlabs website visitors by country

The most visited pages, after the homepage, are the page with information on the TA call, the general news (with 99 news published), the events page and the description of the research facilities, demonstrating the high interest of visitors for this activity of the project.

	21,222 100% of total	2,472 100% of total
<input type="checkbox"/> Total		
<input type="checkbox"/> 1 /	4,360 (20.54%)	1,071 (43.33%)
<input type="checkbox"/> 2 /access/ta-call/	1,396 (6.58%)	308 (12.46%)
<input type="checkbox"/> 3 /news-general/	1,200 (5.65%)	213 (8.62%)
<input type="checkbox"/> 4 /dissemination/event-directory/	992 (4.67%)	189 (7.65%)
<input type="checkbox"/> 5 /access/research-facilities/	946 (4.46%)	370 (14.97%)
<input type="checkbox"/> 6 /networking/training/	680 (3.2%)	150 (6.07%)
<input type="checkbox"/> 7 /dissemination/deliverables/	590 (2.78%)	158 (6.39%)
<input type="checkbox"/> 8 /access/about-ta/	526 (2.48%)	226 (9.14%)
<input type="checkbox"/> 9 /about-us/objectives/	500 (2.36%)	281 (11.37%)
<input type="checkbox"/> 10 /dissemination/publications/	435 (2.05%)	137 (5.54%)

Figure 10. Mostly visited pages of the Co-UDlabs website

1.1.4. Social networks and online presence

Social media have been used to inform and stay connected with the professionals, policy makers and scientific community as well as reach out to an interested general public.

A **LinkedIn page** and a **Twitter/X account** were created in the first months of the project to develop a community of people interested in the project, to raise awareness on the project launch and objectives and to allow for more interaction with related initiatives:

- LinkedIn page: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/co-udlabs-project/>
- X account: <https://x.com/CoUDlabs>

LinkedIn and Twitter users are very active, web-savvy and heavy internet users, thereby improving the visibility of the Co-UDlabs messages. These have proved to be very useful channels to enhance the visibility of publications, newsletters, project members participation in conferences/events (improving networking) and the dissemination of any important activities related to the project. Partners are encouraged by UDC and Euronovia to actively participate by sharing news, articles about their work and regular information on the project developments, to initiate discussions and provoke debates. Such peer-to-peer insights delivered to personal professional contacts can be very effective in creating awareness and impact on the project.

Figure 11. Co-UDlabs LinkedIn page and Twitter account

The impact of Twitter can be analysed through Twitter Analytics while the impact of the LinkedIn page is accessible by the group administrators:

- At M48, the project **LinkedIn group** hits **651 subscribers** and **182 posts**. Below are some interesting analytics data concerning LinkedIn visitors in the final year (older statistics are not available anymore, but data of previous years has been archived by Euronovia).

Visitors location	Total followers	Industry	Total views	Job function	Total views
Beaumont, France	35	Civil Engineering	114	Research	82
Ruhr Region, Germany	33	Research Services	55	Education	78
Greater Magdeburg Area, Germany	24	Environmental Services	39	Engineering	36
Greater Oviedo Metropolitan Area, Spain	24	Utilities	30	Business Development	19
Greater Lyon Area, France	22	Higher Education	26	Media and Communication	12
Greater Ferrol Metropolitan Area, Spain	20	Renewable Energy Equipment Manufacturing	23	Program and Project Management	11
Zürich Metropolitan Area, Switzerland	17	Engineering Services	16	Administrative	9
Greater Paris Metropolitan Region, France	11	Software Development	15	Information Technology	7
Guadalajara, Mexico Metropolitan Area, Mexico	10	IT Services and IT Consulting	15	Community and Social Services	6
Brussels Metropolitan Area, Belgium	10	Water, Waste, Steam, and Air Conditioning Services	14		
The Randstad, Netherlands, Netherlands	9	Government Administration	13		
Greater Karlsruhe Area, Germany	9	Hospitals and Health Care	9		
Birjand, Iran	9	Architecture and Planning	9		
Greater Toronto Area, Canada, Canada	9	Non-profit Organizations	7		
Greater Munich Metropolitan Area, Germany	8	Air, Water, and Waste Program Management	7		
Greater Bologna Metropolitan Area, Italy	8	Maritime Transportation	7		
Bogotá D.C. Metropolitan Area, Colombia	8				
Greater Cádiz Metropolitan Area, Spain	7				
Greater Vancouver Metropolitan Area, Canada	7				

Figure 12. Co-UDlabs LinkedIn users' profiles

- The project **Twitter account** has **217 followers**, with **315 published tweets**. In addition, several partners used their institutional LinkedIn and Twitter accounts to communicate about the project, some of them being very active on social media and with an important number of followers. More analytics data can be provided upon request.

1.1.5. Press relations

Co-UDlabs published several articles to inspire and engage the citizens and to reach a higher level of the importance of innovating urban drainage systems. Different types of press and media coverage took place during the lifetime of the project:

- 22 external articles** have been published about Co-UDlabs in regional and national online and print media

Articles	Published in	Date of publication	Dissemination level
Investigadores de la UDC lideran un proyecto europeo de estudio de sistemas de saneamiento urbano	www.iAgua.es	April 2021	National
El saneamiento urbano, a revisión	www.laopinioncoruña.es	April 2021	National
Temos que ir cara sistemas máis sostibles e intelixentes	https://osil.info/	June 2021	Regional
IKT in EU-Laborforschungsverbund: Forschung und Innovationskraft für städtische Entwässerungssysteme	https://irf.nrw/	June 29, 2021	Regional
Le laboratoire DEEP participe au projet européen Co-UDlabs	https://www.insavalor.fr/	August 2021	National
Le Graie prend part au projet européen Co-UDlabs	www.constructioncayola.com	August 27, 2021	National
Eaux pluviales urbaines : le Graie engagé dans un programme européen	www.enviscope.com	September 29, 2021	National
Infraestructura coruñesa al servicio del saneamiento	www.laopinioncoruña.es	October 2021	Regional
Co-UDlabs: Forschung und Innovationskraft stärken	BI Umweltbau	June 2021	National
La Universidade, sede de la primera asamblea del proyecto europeo sobre drenaje	www.laopinioncoruña.es	June 2022	Regional
A Universidade da Coruña acollerá tres equipos de investigación internacionais que realizarán ensaios punteiros sobre inundacións en contornas urbanas	www.21noticias.com	July 2022	Local
La UDC acogerá a tres equipos internacionales que investigarán sobre inundaciones urbanas	www.elespanol.com/quincemil	July 2022	Regional

<u>L'ambition est de sortir les résultats de recherche des cartons pour améliorer la gestion de l'eau urbaine</u>	www.actu-environnement.com	July 19, 2022	National
<u>Städtische Entwässerungssysteme – Treffen des europäischen Forschungskonsortiums in A Coruña</u>	https://jrf.nrw/	August 8, 2022	Regional
<u>Digitalisierung in der Abwasserentsorgung – ein wichtiger Baustein zur Lösung der globalen Wasserkrise</u>	https://jrf.nrw/	September 19, 2022	Regional
<u>El proyecto europeo liderado por la Universidad de A Coruña, 'Co-udlabs', cierra su convocatoria transnacional</u>	https://www.elidealgallego.com/articulo/a-coruna/proyecto-europeo-liderado-universidad-coruna-co-udlabs-cierra-convocatoria-transnacional-4721314	February 15, 2024	Regional
<u>Spitzenforschung im Untergrund</u>	https://www.eawag.ch/	March 11, 2024	National
<u>Wo die Abwasser erzählen</u>	https://www.horizonte-magazin.ch/	March 7, 2024	National
<u>O CITEEC da UDC abre as súas portas ao público co gallo da Semana Verde da UE</u>	<u>O CITEEC da UDC abre as súas portas ao público co gallo da Semana Verde da UE - 21NOTICIAS</u>	June 18, 2024	Regional
<u>... Y A Coruña creó la lluvia</u>	https://www.elidealgallego.com/articulo/a-coruna/mayor-simulador-lluvia-europa-encuentra-centro-innovacion-udc-4879538	June 21, 2024	Regional
<u>A UDC acollerá un Workshop Internacional sobre Computación Aplicada ao Experimento LHCB do Centro Europeo de Investigación Nuclear</u>	https://21noticias.com/2025/01/25/a-udc-acollera-un-workshop-internacional-sobre-computacion-aplicada-ao-experimento-lhcb-do-centro-europeo-de-investigacion-nuclear/	January 25, 2025	Regional
<u>A Universidade da Coruña presenta en Bruxelas os resultados do proxecto europeo Co-UDlabs sobre os sistemas de drenaxe urbana - 21NOTICIAS</u>	<u>A Universidade da Coruña presenta en Bruxelas os resultados do proxecto europeo Co-UDlabs sobre os sistemas de drenaxe urbana - 21NOTICIAS</u>	March 20, 2025	Regional

Table 1. Press articles published by Co-UDlabs partners

In addition, the project coordinator presented Co-UDlabs during a radio interview on a Spanish regional radio in April 2021: <https://www.crtvg.es/rg/destacados/a-tarde-a-tarde-do-dia-29-04-2021-5012510>. Elodie Brelot from GRAIE presented the Co-UDlabs project during a filmed interview by Actu Environment in June 29, 2022: <https://youtu.be/vjD8WLFPzL4>.

- **1 final media press kit** has been done at M46 for dissemination to the press and to participants in the final infoday to show project and TA programme results. The final media press kit is available on the project website (https://co-udlabs.eu/wp-content/uploads/2025/03/CoUDlabs_PressKit_WEB.pdf) and has been distributed during the Co-UDlabs final event.

Figure 13. Co-UDlabs Final media press kit

The Co-UDlabs project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101008626.

1.1.6. Policy briefs

We have published the first Co-UDlabs Policy Brief on Combined Sewer Overflow (CSO) spills, that was presented during the final InfoDay. It is available for download at: <https://zenodo.org/records/15081107>.

UDC will coordinate the preparation of two additional Policy Briefs related with Research Infrastructures and permeable pavement clogging, which will be available after the end of the project on the Co-UDlabs website and Zenodo community.

These papers provide some policy recommendations to address key aspects of the urban drainage sector.

1.1.7. Scientific and technical publications

During the project, the Co-UDlabs consortium published several articles both in scientific (for academic) and technical (for practitioners) journals to widely disseminate the project outcomes and support its results.

During the project lifetime, partners have published:

- **11 journal papers** in 8 different journals: Environmental Science Water Research & Technology, Urban Water Journal, Water Research X, Journal of Hydrology, Water Science and Technology, Nature Reviews Earth & Environment, Blue-Green Systems, Science of the Total Environment
- **28 conference papers** following participation in 11 different conferences and events at the national (*XIV Seminario de la Red de Laboratorios de Hidráulica de España, CONGRESO. Asociación Española de Abastecimientos de Agua y Saneamiento AEAS 2023 and AEAS 2024, VII Jornadas de Ingeniería del Agua, XV Congreso Español De Tratamiento De Aguas*) and international level (*Proceedings of the 39th IAHR World Congress, Proceedings of the 10th International Conference on Sewer Processes and Networks, Novatech 2023, The International Scientific and Practical Conference on Modern aspects of microbiology, virology, and biotechnology in wartime and post-war period, ICUD 2024, ICWS*).
- **3 technical articles** in national journals (TecnoAqua, Spain; Rioned and Stowa, Germany; Astee TSM, France)

The full list is available in Annex 1.

In addition, there are currently **several other publications planned** to be published in the upcoming weeks, which are either in preparation or under review:

7 journal papers:

- “The value of urban drainage systems data: facts, discussions and recommendations”, Alejandra Pimiento, Jose Anta, in Journal of Hydraulic Research (submitted)
- “Towards standardized methods to assess long-term hydrological performance of permeable pavements by laboratory tests”, Juan Naves, Marcel Goerke, in Construction and Building Materials (in preparation)
- “Benchmarking of different techniques - technologies to determine DEM in UDS”, Esteban Sañudo, Juan Naves, in Journal of Hydrology (in preparation)
- “An experimental investigation of buildings storage effect on pluvial flooding”, Vasilis Bellos, Spyros Pritsis, Juan Naves, in Hydrological Processes (submitted)

- “Experiments on contaminant transport from sewer infrastructure within shallow floodwater”, Shucksmith J. D., Addison-Atkinson W., Fagour C., Gostiaux L., Nathalie G., Nichols A., Mignot E., Muraro F., Rubinato M., in Journal of Hydraulic Research (submitted)
- “Influence of grate geometry on hydraulic energy losses in a surcharged manhole under flood conditions”, Brazier K, Shucksmith J, Nichols A, Rubinato M, Martins R in Urban Water Journal (in preparation)
- “Experimental and Numerical Study of the Hydrodynamics of Manholes During Flood Conditions”, Muraro, F, Martins, R, Rubinato, M, Shucksmith, J, in Journal of Hydrology (in preparation)

3 technical articles:

- “The UDMT software for metrology in urban drainage: methods and examples of application” by INSA in the Water Practice & Technology journal (submission planned in May 2025)
- “The role of Research Infrastructures in urban drainage systems” by UDC in the Journal of Hydraulic Research or IAHR white paper series (in preparation)
- “Rôle possible des infrastructures de recherche dans l’évolution des pratiques et de la réglementation en matière de gestion des eaux pluviales en Europe by GRAIE in Astee TSM (submission planned in May 2025).

1.1.8. Events

The Co-UDlabs project partners organized and participated in several public events to promote the project and disseminate the results.

1.1.8.1. Events organised by project partners

During the project lifetime, project partners organized several events with different dissemination scopes: seminars for industry professionals and early-stage researchers, workshops and special sessions at international conferences, public webinars and online lectures for specific and emerging monitoring techniques in UD, online and physical workshops to disseminate the project results achieved in WP6, WP7 and WP8, webinars and hackathons to promote the TA calls and a final Info Day targeting a wide audience.

In total, **31 events were organised by the Co-UDlabs project partners**, with **900 people reached**. The full list is available in Annex 2.

1.1.8.2. Participation in external events

Co-UDlabs was presented in a series of different national and international events by project partners, who engaged with specialist groups of stakeholders as ambassadors of the project to raise awareness of its activities and results.

The consortium participated in **53 external events** for promotion and scientific dissemination where partners presented the work done within the project with an oral or poster presentation. This includes **19 scientific conferences, 16 national technical events, 4 exhibition trades, 7 open science events, 7 other events**. The full list is available in Annex 3.

The estimated number of people reached during these events is **over 5000**.

In addition, some partners are currently planning their participation in events that are taking place after the end of the project, where Co-UDlabs outputs will be presented:

- Participation of USFD in the **EWA/NWA Spring Seminar 2025**: Shaping the Future of Water Management in Europe on May 28, 2025 in Oslo, Norway. USFD will present an overview of findings from D6.4 and D2.5.
- Oral presentation of USFD at the **SimHydro 2025** in June 2025 in Nice, France (abstract accepted).
- Oral presentation of GRAIE at the Astee conference in June 2025 in Toulouse, France (abstract accepted).
- Organisation of a Co-UDlabs workshop at the 13th **Urban Drainage Modelling Conference (UDM)** taking place on 15-19 September 2025 in Innsbruck, Austria. The workshop will consist of two 90-minute sessions: 1) Co-UDlabs ecosystem catalogue of open datasets of sensors and technologies. How to make data more accessible, reusable and interoperable; 2) Presentation of UDRAIN WG Atlas and next steps for consolidating RI Infrastructures. More information: <https://www.uibk.ac.at/en/congress/udm2025/program/workshops/>. At this conference, USFD will also deliver an oral presentation (abstract accepted).

1.2. Tracking and monitoring the actions

The partner in charge of communication (Euronovia) was responsible for tracking and monitoring all the communication and dissemination activities of the partners to check if the action plan was being carried out properly and on time and to assess which activities had the biggest impact on the stakeholders (both in quantitative and qualitative terms).

At this scope, an Excel table composed of 3 different spreadsheets was created in June 2021 to gather information related to the activities implemented by each partner, namely: communication actions, scientific dissemination activities and scientific publications. This was subsequently updated to include information on publications in preparation and events/ trainings organized by project partners.

This document has been uploaded to the project SharePoint platform and all partners were regularly reminded to update it by listing the communication and dissemination activities they were involved in, including some performance indicators.

This document allowed Euronovia to evaluate the impact of the actions, the type and number of people reached and to check if KPIs planned have been met. This tracking document is available upon request to Euronovia, WP4 leader.

Communication channel (please select from the drop-down list)	Name of the communication source/channel	Title	Date	Place	Links to the event or other online resource	Target Audiences								Outreach level (please select from the drop-down list)	Partner in charge	
						Academics and researchers	Industry/Policy-makers	Government/ Policy-makers	EU/International networks	National technology networks	EU projects	General public/industry groups				
55	News in website	JRF website (www.jrf.nrw), a website of Johannes-Rau-Forschungsgemeinschaft - regional Research Association of 15 independent research institutes of the region Northrhine-Westfalia (Germany)	19 September 2022	online	https://jrf.nrw/veranstaltung/digitalisierung-in-der-abwasserentsorgung-ein-wichtiger-baustein-zur-loesung-der-globalen-wasserkrise-ikt-und-seine-europaeischen-partner-organisierten-workshop-auf-dem-iwa-world-water-congress-amp-exhibition-2022-wwce-in-kopenhagen	x		x							Regional	IKT
56	News in website	Actu-environnement	19/07/2022	online	https://www.actu-environnement.com/actu/news/video-lyc-graie-elodie-brelot-recherche-techniques-alternatives-gestion-eaux-pluviales-ville			x	x						National	GRAIE
57	Video	Actu-environnement	19/07/2022	online	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=viD8WlFPt4			x	x						National	GRAIE
58	News in website	JRF website (www.jrf.nrw), a website of Johannes-Rau-Forschungsgemeinschaft - regional Research Association of 15 independent research institutes of the region Northrhine-Westfalia (Germany)	19/09/2022	online	https://jrf.nrw/veranstaltung/digitalisierung-in-der-abwasserentsorgung-ein-wichtiger-baustein-zur-loesung-der-globalen-wasserkrise-ikt-und-seine-europaeischen-partner-organisierten-workshop-auf-dem-iwa-world-water-congress-amp-exhibition-2022-wwce-in-kopenhagen	x			x						Regional	IKT

Table 2: Overview of the online form tracking partners' communication and dissemination actions

1.3. Impact assessment

A detailed communication and dissemination plan was created at M6 to monitor the correct implementation of the activities planned in the GA, integrating **Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)** to measure the impact of each dissemination and communication activity. KPI's are a measuring factor for the performance and progress of an activity, message, task, etc. towards its expected impact. Several KPIs have been defined for each communication and dissemination activity. KPIs were used to assess the performance of the dissemination activities all along the project duration: an update was presented at each consortium meeting to provide partners with an overview of the consortium performance with regards to communication and dissemination and to warn them in case of underperformance, so that they could take action to improve certain KPIs without delays.

Using inputs from partners to the document tracking communication and dissemination actions, we elaborated a **dissemination impact analysis** to evaluate the impact of these actions. The following scale was used to score each KPI:

- If the results are lower than 50% of the target, the result is considered as Low
- If the results are lower or equal to 75% but above 50%, the result is considered as Moderate
- If the results are lower or equal to 100% but above 75%, the result is considered as Good
- If the results are higher than 100%, the result is considered as High

The analysis shows a very satisfying performance: as summarised in the table below, **77% of our KPIs have received either a “High” or a “Good” score**, with only 14% having received a moderate score, and 9% a low score. The low scores refer to the low number of technical papers published (it is to be noted that 3 more are currently in preparation) and to the low number of participants in certain Co-UDlabs events. This is balanced by a very good participation in other Co-UDlabs events, a very good performance of the communication and dissemination material and activities and very good scores related to scientific publications.

The in-depth analysis KPIs reached at M48, compared to targets that have been set to measure the success of the communication and dissemination actions, is available in Annex 4.

Score	High	Good	Moderate	Low
% of KPI	59%	18%	14%	9%

Table 3: KPIs' performance at M48

In addition to quantitative KPIs, some **qualitative indicators** were taken into consideration to understand the impact of the actions carried out, for example:

- Individual feedback obtained through satisfaction questionnaires sent to participants after project events: we have sent out questionnaires to participants in the hackathon and the workshop organised before the launch of the TA calls and we received a few responses with very good feedback on the content and utility of these events for the participants. Responses to these questionnaires can be provided to the EC upon request.
- Feedback obtained from users of the RIs: a questionnaire was sent to TA users to collect feedback on the quality and process of the Co-UDlabs Transnational Access programme. More than 40 answers were collected, providing a very positive feedback and useful information on how every aspect of the process was perceived (more details available in Deliverable 9.2). This feedback was taken into consideration when planning the 2nd call for Transnational Access. In addition, we collected the 13 testimonials of the RIs users of the first TA call, which are very positive and have been gathered into a dedicated factsheet (https://co-udlabs.eu/wp-content/uploads/2023/07/TA_call_factsheet_testimonials.pdf).

2. Plan for exploitation of project results

To ensure Co-UDlabs maximises its impact by exploiting results, the project plan for exploitation complements the aforementioned dissemination and communication activities ensuring the continued targeted impact of all knowledge transfer activities to foster exploitation of Co-UDlabs results. In its nature, Co-UDlabs holds the potential for exploiting research outputs at various levels involving different types of organizations, such as water utilities, the SMEs in their supply chain, research centres as well as other public interest organizations, for the benefit of the final users of the RIs. The plan for exploitation takes into consideration these different levels through the different aspects presented below:

- **Target groups identification:** lead (technology makers) and end users principally, and/or potential future competitors.
- **Identification of project outputs** and explanation on how to proceed with their development.
- **Definition of the exploitation strategy:** we selected the most promising project outputs (i.e. Key Exploitable Results) and we defined the partners' exploitation intentions, risk assessment, use options, exploitation roadmap and characterization table. In the upcoming weeks, the Key Exploitable Results of the project will be uploaded to the Horizon Results Platform (<https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/portal/screen/opportunities/horizon-results-platform>) to boost dissemination and maximize chances of being discovered by the right stakeholders for valorisation purposes.
- **Methods for exploitation** – All captured knowledge was assessed and recorded in line with the Consortium Agreement (CA), respecting privacy and Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) requirements. This approach is essential to avoid unforeseen delays or obstacles related to confidentiality or competitiveness and to provide partners with the security they need to allow them to be transparent in their findings, enabling the project to quickly identify opportunities for exploitation. Then, the range of different possibilities for exploitation was discussed by project partners for each KER in order to develop the appropriate plan, considering the nature of the partner(s) involved in the dissemination and exploitation.

2.1. List of Key Exploitable Results

The major project outputs that were considered to have the most value for exploitation were already identified at the proposal stage. However, this list was updated by the consortium under the lead of Euronovia during RP2 (second half of 2023), when WP leaders were asked to update this initial list taking into consideration all the knowledge outputs developed or to be developed within each WP by the end of the project. This was done through several meetings and interviews with partners.

As a result of this process, partners identified 10 KERs. An overview of this list is available in Table 4 below, while the detailed list is available upon request to Euronovia.

As a second step, to receive expert guidance and to optimize its exploitation strategy, the consortium requested support from the **Horizon Results Booster** service (Module C). Experts of the Booster asked partners to select the 3 KERs which were considered as the most relevant for in-depth analysis.

For each of these 3 KERs (highlighted in light blue in Table 4) partners involved in its creation or interested in its exploitation worked together to jointly define exploitation intentions and roles, characterisation table, risk assessment and priority map, use options and exploitation roadmap. This information, which was requested by the

experts of the Booster, served as a guide for discussions during the exploitation seminar organised online in February 2024.

This seminar was helpful in pushing partners to review the list of KERs of the project, to jointly reflect on the exploitation aspects of the project, to collaboratively revise and clarify the existing exploitation plans and ownership of project results as well as barriers and opportunities for their uptake. It was also an opportunity for partners to start thinking about future developments and possible funding mechanisms to ensure exploitation of results after the end of the project.

During the seminar, the consortium received guidance from two assigned experts to improve the existing project strategies towards effective exploitation of Key Exploitable Results. The main outcome of this seminar is a **series of tools and guidelines** for the consortium to make the most out of the exploitation activities of the project as well as a final report including KERs analysis and recommendations for partners (available upon request to Euronovia).

#	Name of the result (to be commercially or non-commercially exploited)	Lead partner (willing or best positioned to exploit the result)	Other partners interested in exploitation	Description	Nature	Open or restricted access	WPs allowing for the development of the result	Future users/beneficiaries
KER 1	Prototype of a non-contact water quality monitoring device	EAWAG	UDC, Deltares	A commercially available camera platform ("Pollutionkeeper") to monitor a set of water quality variables without direct contact to the wastewater	Other (please specify in comments)	Open Access	WP6	SMEs, practitioners, scientists, water utilities
KER 2	Strategic agenda on urban drainage research infrastructures - UDRAIN	GRAIE	UDC, all scientific partners	Clarification and illustration of principles, levers, organisation and practical solutions to facilitate the transfer and appropriation of research results into practice and regulations	Methodology	Open Access	WP1 and all WPs because Co-Udlabs is an experimentation	Policy makers (national and international level) and scientists
KER 3	UDMT - Urban Drainage Metrology Toolbox	INSA	Deltares, UDC, GRAIE	A series of tools / methods / algorithms to promote best practices in urban drainage metrology and monitoring	Software	Open Access	WP6	practitioners, scientists, students
KER 4	Toronto Exfiltration System	USFD		This is a novel configuration of a drainage system that combines infiltration with normal flow transport. The aim is to increase the flow capacity of buried stormwater systems without increasing the asset footprint.	Methodology	Restricted access	WP9	Engineering consultancies, water utilities
KER 5	Tekno-soil design for infiltration based SUDS	AAU	INSA, UDC	Model for predicting infiltration and pollutant transport of infiltration soil	Model	Restricted access	WP8	Water utilities Design Engineers, SMEs
KER 6	Creation of new services or products on data management, buried assets evaluation and rehabilitation	USFD	IKT, DEL	Codes to access the impact of operational and structural defects	Software	Open Access	WP2, WP6, WP7	PhD students, post-doctoral Researchers, water utilities, SMEs from outside water sector, e.g. Microsoft/Siemens
KER 7	Data management toolboxes	Deltares	EAWAG, UDC,	Platforms on which stakeholders can participate in sharing views on data, ontologies and dataformats	Standardisation	Open Access	WP2, WP3	Researchers, utilities and large managing organizations involved in UD, SMEs building data-based services
KER 8	Training content	Deltares		Free training courses on UD	Training program	Open Access	WP3	Early-stage researchers, students, water engineering consultants
KER 9	Camera system to track flow velocities, depths and other features	UDC	DEL, USFD, EAWAG	An edge computing systems on RaspberryPi to track flow velocities, depths in UDS. Some applications on UDC models and Aalborg Pond	Other (please specify in comments)	Open Access	WP8	practitioners, scientists, water utilities, SMEs
KER 10	Sediment detection and monitoring device using temperature signals (MONTSE)	EAWAG	UDC, EAWAG	Probe to detect bed sediment elevation using temperature signal in different urban drainage infrastructures	Other (please specify in comments)	Open Access	WP8, TA	practitioners, scientists, water utilities, SMEs

Table 4: Final list of Co-UDlabs Key Exploitable Results (KERs)

2.2. Lean Canvas of Co-UDlabs KERs

Among their recommendations, the experts suggested continuing to discuss practical and strategical aspects of exploitation, to further develop, update and validate what discussed during the seminar and to do a similar work for

the other KERs which were not analysed by the Booster, especially using Lean Canvas. The Lean Canvas is an adaptation of Business Model Canvas, redesigned by Ash Maurya to be more actionable and entrepreneur-focused including aspects for startups to deal with uncertainty and risk. It focuses on problems, solutions, key metrics and competitive advantages. The canvas is a good tool to focus on the exploitation model and start collecting information for the exploitation plan and it is the most suited for R&D projects. It is considered to be a powerful tool to be used by the partners to further develop the characterization of their KERs, prepare the materials to be discussed at consortium meetings and draft the exploitation/business plan for a KER.

Following these recommendations, in the final year of the project, Euronovia coordinated the work on exploitation by guiding partners to fill a Lean Canvas for each KER (including the 3 KERs analysed by the Booster).

This tool allowed partners to either work on or update their KERs' characterisation and helped them to fine-tune and develop the exploitation strategy for their KERs, having in mind the following questions:

- Description of the problems addressed
- Existing alternatives to address the same problems
- Description of the results/solution proposed
- Its Unique Value Proposition
- Its advantages
- Target customers
- Early adopters
- Channels to reach these customers and early adopters
- Key aspects/activities to track the success of the solution
- Revenue streams
- Cost structure

The end goal of the Lean Canvas is that an unknowing third-party will be able to review it from start to end and, through this revision, understand what the KER is about. They will understand the problem in focus, the customer groups targeted, the solution provided, how it differentiates from competitors, etc.

After several interactions among partners and Euronovia, Lean Canvas have been developed for the 10 Co-UDlabs KERs. They are available in Annex 5.

2.3. Actions to achieve the exploitation of results and impacts of the project

Several types of actions were planned in the GA to ensure exploitation of results before and after the end of the project. An update on the effective implementation of these actions is provided in the Table 5 below.

Table 5: Actions planned to achieve the exploitation of results

Type of actions	Description	Targeted groups	Status at M48
During the project			
Events	Organisation of several training workshops (industrial workshops and summer schools) addressing the main technology application of the RI project. Creation of training content.	The R&D sector, the academic and non-academic organizations with specific players in the field, the public at	Several trainings have already been organised by project partners: webinars, trainings for early-stage researchers and trainings for industry professionals. Full list available at https://co-udlabs.eu/networking/training/

		large, related EU projects	
Events	Organisation of Novatech side event (WP1). Participation in practitioners and policy-makers national and international events (WP4)	The different international Urban Drainage research community users and policy makers.	The Co-UDlabs workshop was organised on July 3, 2024 to launch the second TA call: https://co-udlabs.eu/events/co-udlabs-workshop-at-novatech-2023/
Events	Local and national meetings to optimize the transmission of knowledge and know how to operators.	The different Urban Drainage community users	16 national technical events attended to date by the Co-UDlabs partners to disseminate its results.
Events	Organisation of one final info day: the impact and further exploitation of the project results will be introduced to a wider public. Virtual attendance will be allowed.	Public at large, policy makers, media, and all other stakeholders	The Co-UDlabs final Info Day was organised on March 18, 2025 in Brussels: https://co-udlabs.eu/2025/03/20/co-udlabs-final-infoday/
Internal event	Exploitation and IPR workshop. Potential licensees and water utilities will be invited.	Consortium	The exploitation workshop was organised within the Horizon Results Booster in February 2024
Internal event	Participation to IPR webinars organized by the IPR EC Helpdesk	Consortium (at least one webinar)	Some of the partners attended at least one IPR webinar organized by the IPR EC Helpdesk.
Engagement of young researchers	New recruitment and engagement of 8 PhD candidates and 5 post-doctoral positions on Co-UDlabs who should be especially relevant candidates for the creation of innovative start-ups.	We raised awareness of IPR and exploitation actions among PhD students and post-docs involved in the project.	Several postdocs and MSc students were recruited by project partners and engaged on Co-UDlabs.
Work package tasks	Activities of WP2 (Smart governance) will be dedicated to providing information and evidence to support the revision of EC Directives related with water sector ¹ (e.g. Bathing water, ICT, Nature Based Solutions, WWTD, etc).	Policy makers and industrials	The Co-UDlabs project partners contributed to the revision of the European Urban Waste Water Treatment Directive (UWWTD) via consultations in 2019, SPN9 in 2019. Six Co-UDlabs partners from Spain, France, Switzerland, UK and Germany have made complete and precise contribution to the public consultation for UWWTD revision in 2021. These responses can be put into perspective with the needs and expectations expressed by 285 respondents, from 22 Member States and 6 other countries (UK, Norway, Switzerland, Serbia, USA and Israel), among which scientists seem to be few. Co-UDlabs' partners also provided feedback to the public consultation on Water Resilience and Water Efficiency initiatives in March 2025.
Collaborations with other projects	Results containing fundamental information, system evaluations, innovative inputs, network publication	Stakeholders from national, EU and international funded projects. EU wide bodies such as WaterEurope or EurEau.	Several collaborations were implemented with the following: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Water associations EWA - IFAT; WATER-EUROPE (Group of NBS) • EU projects Project VITALISE; EUROPLANET SOCIETY, WATER4ALL, D4runoff • National projects SATURNO, DigitalRAIN, SUDSlong
Creation of an International Advisory Board	Ensure the management of innovation within the consortium and guarantee that all effective measures are taken to maximize the dissemination and potential exploitation of the results during and after the project. This board will include key actors in the target areas and will be	Consortium actors in the development of Key Exploitable Results	The IAB was constituted at the proposal stage and it brings powerful stakeholders to the table, such as EurEau (EU level network of water operators), IKT Association of Industry (70 companies from the private), SUEZ France (global expert in the water and waste sectors), RTO SINTEF (an independent research organization with 2000 employees from

¹ <https://ec.europa.eu/info/law/better-regulation/have-your-say>

	used as a tool to advise on related issues such as public acceptance, local regulations, set up of adequate and fair incentive schemes and the exploitation of the project results.		75 countries), and two leading scientists from Université Laval (Canada) and University of New South Wales (Australia).
After the project			
Research development	Future internal research at the partners' institutions will be carried out to ensure the further sustainability of the technology development and upgrade. The results will be used as background for future collaborative innovation projects. This should take place potentially through new EU funding (like the COST actions to favour networking on a targeted R&D topic) or national funding targeting knowledge transfer between academia and industry.	Consortium partners and new key actors in the field, especially targeting the industry actors	Several research projects based on the results of Co-UDLabs have been funded, with the participation of Co-UDlabs partners: ETHdomain - OpenResearchData project; Innosuisse - R&D project Pollutionkeeper; H2020 - URBAN M2O, inspired by Co-UDLabs and containing a TA-element and harmonized data management systems.
Creation of new services and products	The new services and products free software tools and methods for data handling (WP2, WP6) could be exploited by the SMEs of the consortium to propose new services or with the creation of spin-off and start-up companies.	SMEs, end users of the project, external industry actors	As part of WP6, a software tool was developed, the Urban Drainage Metrology Toolbox (UDMT), for the calibration and correction of sensors, for calculating the uncertainties in data (type A, type B, Monte-Carlo), for data validation, and for tracing experiments. This is available as a free to use online web app and an offline executable application. The user manual, the executable version, the training examples data sets, the Matlab source code of the final version 2025a are available on Zenodo.
Further funding	PPP, EU funding for innovation (especially the SMEs instruments, such as Eurostars SMEs instrument), public procurement, venture capitals, private investors, banks, business angels will be sought for, to ensure the further development of the RI .	End users of the project, investors	Further funding for a Co-UDlabs follow-up project is currently being explored by partners.
Standards	The possibility for providing inputs to European standards in the manufacturing sector will be also deepened.	Standardization sector	UDC and IKT are preparing a manuscript about the needs for standardized tests for permeable pavement. This will be available after the end of the project.
Policy Roadmap	A wide dissemination of the roadmap will ensure that stakeholders engage with the project results even after the end of the project.	Industrial and policy makers, including international policy makers like the IEA or IRENA	The document "Roadmap of RI required to support effective UDS transition at EU level" is the deliverable D1.2, which was submitted on October 2024 by GRAIE. The aim of this document is to collect information from different stakeholders and identify what practices RI need to change or continue doing to help optimise urban drainage (UD) management. The Roadmap is available on Zenodo: https://zenodo.org/records/15256037 . Also, Co-UDlabs promotes the UDRAIN working group of the Joint Committee of Urban Drainage (JCUD). UDRAIN seeks to establish a worldwide network of large RIs of UD systems to foster cooperation, technical collaboration, and joint initiatives. This will continue after the end of the project. See deliverable D1.3 for more information, as well as the following publication: https://zenodo.org/records/8017076 .
Open databases	Permanent access to the main results of the project in different databases, including Zenodo and OpenAIRE.	All interested stakeholders	All project datasets are made available in the Co-UDlabs community on Zenodo: https://zenodo.org/communities/coudlabs/

2.4. Protection of results and IP

The overall Intellectual Property (IP) approach of the project is in line and builds on the principles and guidelines described in the European Commission Recommendations on the management of intellectual property in knowledge transfer activities and Code of Practice for universities and other public research organisations, along three main aspects: (i) internal IP management; (ii) knowledge transfer activities; (iii) collaborative and contract research.

For internal IP management, a Consortium Agreement was signed between all partners to address all relevant issues related to IP and the results generated during the project (access rights to background and foreground necessary for the execution of the Project, rules for dissemination and use of own knowledge). The Consortium Agreement (CA) complements the rules of the Grant Agreement. In particular, treatment of partners' background, the disclosure of new ideas with potential commercial interest, the ownership of research and results, record keeping and confidentiality, are all elements tackled in the consortium agreement.

In general, IP is the property of the partners and facility users that have contributed to the creation of the knowledge. The degree of ownership depends on the degree of contribution to the IP. This general rule applies as long as it does not violate national legislation, specific agreements for scientific publication, and specific agreements among partners regarding ownership of IP. Partners that have jointly carried out work generating foreground and where their respective share of work cannot be ascertained shall have joint ownership of that foreground and may establish appropriate joint ownership agreements or license agreements. This task is considered essential as a guarantee for the good implementation of the project.

Further to the draft of the CA, the coordinator had an active role in providing advice and recommendations to the project partners and to implement innovation management actions. Further to the start of the project, the coordinator made sure that all partners were aware of the IP policy (presentation at the Kick-off meeting) and that the partners supported the Code of Practice concerning the management of IP as stated by the recommendation from the European Commission (i.e. to better convert knowledge into socio-economic benefits, to more effectively exploit publicly-funded research results with a view to translating them into new products and services, ...). Partners were recommended to attend one of the webinars on IP organised by the IP Helpdesk to boost the understanding of the consortium on these matters.

As regards to the rules for dissemination activities, any beneficiary had the possibility to object to dissemination if it could show that it would suffer significant harm (in relation to background or results) and could delay its dissemination to safeguard the interests at stake. For the dissemination, the Grant Agreement rules were followed (45 days prior notice before any dissemination). At partner level, there was a periodical review of the results created by each partner and all partners were encouraged to protect any knowledge that had potential commercial applications.

In addition, a Facility User Agreement was signed for TA access of the different User groups with the Facility provider to address all the relevant issues related with the access and with the IP and results generated during the project. This agreement was signed just for the access to the RIs and defined Open access data policies.

Annex 1. List of publications

Journal papers:

- “Towards urban drainage sediment accumulation monitoring using temperature sensors”, M. Regueiro-Picallo, J. Anta, A. Naves, A. Figueroa, J. Rieckermann, *Environmental Science Water Research & Technology*
- “European stakeholders’ visions and needs for stormwater in future urban drainage systems”, Katharina Tondera, Elodie Brelot, Fanny Fontanel, Frédéric Cherqui, Jesper Ellerbæk Nielse, Thomas Brüggemann, Iain Naismith, Marcel Goerke, Joaquín Suárez López Jörg Rieckermann, João P. Leitaó, François H.L.R. Clemens-Meyer, Antonio Moreno-Rodenas, Simon Tait & José Anta, *Urban Water Journal*
- “Combining a daily temperature pattern analysis and a heat-pulse system to estimate sediment depths in sewer systems”, M. Regueiro-Picallo, J. Langeveld, H. Wei, J.-L. Bertrand-Krajewski, J. Rieckermann, *Environmental Science Water Research & Technology*
- “Towards non-contact pollution monitoring in sewers with hyperspectral imaging”, P. Lechevallier, C. Felsheim, Villez, K., J. Rieckermann, *Environmental Science Water Research & Technology*
- “Low-cost monitoring systems for urban water management: Lessons from the field”, [...] Frederic Cherqui, Nicolas Walcker, Jean-Luc Bertrand-Krajewski [...], *Water Research X*
- “Sets of infiltration models for water infiltration in sustainable urban”, Asra Asry, Gislain Lipeme Kouyi, Tim D. Fletcher, Jeremie Bonneau, Damien Tedoldi, Laurent Lassabatere, *Journal of Hydrology*
- “Measuring heat transfer processes in gully pots for real-time estimation of accumulated sediment depths”, M. Regueiro-Picallo, A. Moreno-Rodenas, F. Clemens-Meyer, *Environmental Science Water Research & Technology*
- “Flow rate influence on sediment depth estimation in sewers using temperature sensors”, Manuel Regueiro-Picallo, Alma Schellart, Henriette Jensen, Jeroen Langeveld, Maria Viklander and Lian Lundy, *Water Science and Technology*
- “Concepts and evolution of urban hydrology”, Tim D. Fletcher, Matthew J. Burns, Kathryn L. Russell, Perrine Hamel, Sophie Duchesne, Frédéric Cherqui & Allison H. Roy, *Nature Reviews Earth & Environment*
- “Large-scale clogging experiments assessing the hydraulic performance of porous asphalt during their service life”, Angélica Vanessa Goya-Heredia, Juan Naves, Joaquín Suárez, Jose Anta, *Blue-Green Systems*
- “Understanding sediment wash-off in road drainage systems under intense rainfall and high sediment masses: Insights from a large-scale modeling facility”, CA Zafra-Mejía, D Hernández-Medina, J Suárez, J Naves, J Anta, *Science of the Total Environment*

Conference proceedings:

- “Co-Udlabs: Una red europea de infraestructuras de investigación en saneamiento y drenaje urbano”, Jose Anta, Jerónimo Puertas, Luis Cea, Joaquín Suárez, Juan Naves, Manuel Regueiro, Andrea Ciambra, *XIV Seminario de la Red de Laboratorios de Hidráulica de España, RLHE*
- “Permeable pavement clogging laboratory experiments using rainfall simulators”, Jose Anta, Joaquín Suárez, *Proceedings of the 39th IAHR World Congress*

- “Monitoring Sewer Sediment Deposits with Passive Temperature Sensors”, Jose Anta, Jörg Rieckermann, *Proceedings of the 39th IAHR World Congress*
- “Improving sediment monitoring strategies based on analysing heat transfer processes in sewer pipes”, Jörg Rieckermann, *Proceedings of the 10th International Conference on Sewer Processes and Networks*
- “How reusable are your data? - Towards truly FAIR open data for urban drainage”, J. Rieckermann, P. Lechevallier, J. Agustsson, L. Rossi, S. Tait, *Proceedings of the 10th International Conference on Sewer Processes and Networks*
- “Machine learning to improve understanding of sewer pipe failures”, Ehsan Kazemi, Will Shepherd, Simon Tait, *Proceedings of the 10th International Conference on Sewer Processes and Networks*
- “Towards non-contact pollution monitoring in sewers with hyperspectral imaging”, P. Lechevallier, C. Felsheim, J. Rieckermann, *Proceedings of the 10th International Conference on Sewer Processes and Networks*
- “Co-Udlabs: Construyendo una red europea de grandes instalaciones de investigación en saneamiento y drenaje urbano”, Jose Anta, Jerónimo Puertas, Luis Cea, Joaquín Suárez, Juan Naves, Manuel Regueiro, Andrea Ciambra, XXXVI CONGRESO. Asociación Española de Abastecimientos de Agua y Saneamiento
- “Monitoring sediment accumulation in urban drainage systems with temperature measurements”, M. Regueiro-Picallo, A. Moreno-Rodenas, F. Clemens-Meyer, J. Rieckermann, *Proceedings of the NOVATECH 2023*
- “Co-UDlabs: una red europea de grandes instalaciones de investigación en drenaje urbano”, Jose Anta, Jerónimo Puertas, Luis Cea, Joaquín Suárez, Juan Naves, Daniel Carreres and Andrea Ciambra, VII Jornadas de Ingeniería del Agua
- “Aplicaciones de visión artificial para la monitorización de sistemas de drenaje urbano”, Juan Naves, Daniel Carreres, Antonio Moreno-Rodenas, Jesper E. Nielsen, Jose Anta, VII Jornadas de Ingeniería del Agua
- “Efecto de almacenamiento de los edificios durante inundaciones urbanas. Un acceso trasnacional del proyecto Co-UDlabs”, Jose Anta, Jerónimo Puertas, Luis Cea, Juan Naves, VII Jornadas de Ingeniería del Agua
- “Testing the effect of hydrological events on the spread of antimicrobial resistant bacteria in freshwater and the use of crispr-cas technology to address antibiotic tolerance”, N Infante, Lm Pérez, J Morató, I Douterelo, H Jensen, E Karunakaran, S Tait, Book of abstract, The International Scientific and Practical Conference "Modern aspects of microbiology, virology, and biotechnology in wartime and post-war period"
- “Houses as reservoirs in urban flood modelling”, Jose Anta, Jerónimo Puertas, Luis Cea, Juan Naves, *Proceedings of the NOVATECH 2023*
- “How to monitor and regulate Combined Sewer Overflows?”, Alma Schellart, Jean-Luc Bertrand-Krajewski, Joerg Rieckermann, Simon Tait, *Proceedings of the NOVATECH 2023*
- “Visions et besoins des parties prenantes européennes pour les futurs systèmes de gestion des eaux pluviales urbaines”, Katharina Tondera, Frederic Cherqui, Simon Tait, Elodie BreLOT, Fanny Fontanel, Jesper Ellerbaek Nielsen, José Anta, Thomas Brüggemann, Iain Naismith, Marcel Goerke, Joaquin Suárez López, Jörg Rieckermann, João Paulo Leitão, François Clemens-Meyer, Antonio Moreno-Rodenas, *Proceedings of the NOVATECH 2023*

- “MONTSE: MONitorización de las Temperaturas de SEdimentos para evaluar su acumulación en sistemas de drenaje urbano”, *M. Regueiro-Picallo, A. Moreno-Rodenas, F. Clemens-Meyer, J. Rieckermann, VII Jornadas de Ingeniería del Agua*
- “Co-UDlabs: FOMENTANDO LA INNOVACIÓN EN LOS SISTEMAS DE DRENAJE URBANO”, *Anta, J; Puertas, J; Cea, L; Suárez, J; Naves, J; Regueiro-Picallo, M; Pimiento, M.A; Ciambra, A.*, Proceedings of the XXXVII CONGRESO. Asociación Española de Abastecimientos de Agua y Saneamiento (AEAS 2024)
- “Understanding the influence of leaf litter on the water balance composition of blue-green infrastructure”, *Prabhat Joshi & Joao Leitao & Jose Anta & Juan Naves*, Proceedings of the ICUD conference 2024
- “Laboratory-scale analysis of road-deposited sediment wash-off: Runoff scenarios under high sediment load”, *Joaquín Suarez & Jose Anta & Juan Naves*, Proceedings of the ICUD conference 2024
- “Evaluation of new flow and water quality monitoring equipment in sewers under realistic flow conditions”, *Daniel Carreres & Jose Anta & Juan Naves*, Proceedings of the ICUD conference 2024
- “Monitoring sediment build-up in gully pots using temperature-based systems”, *M. Regueiro-Picallo, L. Fuchs, J. Rieckermann, A. Moreno-Rodenas, F. Clemens-Meyer*, Proceedings of the ICUD conference 2024
- “Flow rate influence on sediment depth estimation using temperature sensors”, *M. Regueiro-Picallo, A. Schellart, H. Jensen, J. Langeveld, M. Viklander, L. Lundy*, Proceedings of the ICUD conference 2024
- “Improving the reproducibility and provenance of urban drainage data and models with RENKU, a platform for sustainable data science”, *A. Chavarría, S. Tait, M. Lepot, J.-L. Bertrand-Krajewski, J. P. Leitão, J. Rieckermann*, Proceedings of the ICUD conference 2024
- “The role of open data in regulating Combined Sewer Overflows”, *A. Schellart, L. Sharp, J.-L. Bertrand-Krajewski, J. Rieckermann, Jose Anta, Frank Blumensaat, Francois Clemens, Ulrich Dittmer, Isabel Douterelo, Günter Gruber, Henriette Jensen, James Shucksmith, Simon Tait, Boud Verbeiren, Luca Vezzaro*, Proceedings of the ICUD conference 2024
- “Spatial analysis of the combined sewer overflow durations in England and Wales”, *C. S. de Vito, A. M. Moreno-Rodenas, A. Schellart, J. Shucksmith & Z. Kapelan*, Proceedings of the ICUD conference 2024
- “Building the urban drainage community: European stakeholders’ visions and needs for Urban Drainage Systems”, *Tondera, K., Legge, A., Brelot, E.*, Proceedings of the ICUD conference 2024
- “European stakeholders’ visions and needs for the role of Nature-based Solutions for stormwater treatment in future urban drainage systems”, *Tondera, K., Legge, A., Brelot, E.*, Proceedings of the ICWS
- “Influence of grate geometry on hydraulic energy losses in a surcharged manhole under flood conditions”, *Brazier, Shucksmith, Nichols*, Proceedings of the ICUD conference 2024
- “Análisis de la movilización de contaminación difusa de carreteras en la Plataforma Científica para Ensayos de Escorrentía Urbana del CITEEC-UDC”, *Joaquín Suarez & Jose Anta & Juan Naves*, Proceedings of XV Congreso Español De Tratamiento De Aguas

Technical articles :

- “Co-UDlabs: promoviendo la investigación e innovación en los sistemas de drenaje urbano”, *Anta Álvarez, Jose; Puertas Agudo, Jerónimo; Cea Gómez, Luís; Suárez López, Joaquín; Naves García-Rendueles, Juan; Regueiro Picallo, Manuel; Pimiento Avella, María Alejandra; Ciambra, Andrea*, TECNOAQUA
- Professioneel Afvalwatertransport “Beoordeling inspectieinstrumenten voor persleidingen: onderzoek in testopstelling” by IKT in the RIONED and Stowa publication (March 2024)
- “Comment optimiser les infrastructures de recherche au niveau européen”, by GRAIE in Astee TSM, the leading technical journal for water and waste professionals in France (March 2025).

Annex 2: Events organised by Co-UDlabs project partners

- Co-UDlabs Introductory Webinar on Transnational Access, organised by UDC on October 13, 2021 (online);
- Co-UDlabs Online Workshop on UD Practice and Research Needs, organised by IKT on November 3-4, 2021 (online);
- Co-UDlabs Hackathon on Transnational Access to RIs, organised by Deltares on November 23-25, 2021 (online);
- Co-UDlabs 25th EJSW - European Junior Scientists Workshop on "Monitoring urban drainage systems and rivers", organized by INSA and DELTARES on May 15-21, 2022 in St-Maurice-en-Valgaudemar (France);
- Co-UDlabs 1st Early-Stage Researchers Seminar, organized by UDC on June 27-28, 2022 in A Coruña (Spain);
- Co-UDlabs live workshop on "Strengthening the links between scientists and practitioners to accelerate the transition towards smart and sustainable urban stormwater management – the Co-UDlabs project" organised by GRAIE at the CGLE Carrefour des gestions locales de l'eau on June 29-30, 2022, Rennes (France);
- Co-UDlabs Workshop on "Urban Drainage Metrology Toolbox", organised as a side-event to the International Conference on Sewer Processes and Networks (SPN) by INSA on August 23, 2022 in Graz (Austria);
- Co-UDlabs session on "Tapping the value of urban drainage systems (UDS) Data" organised as part of the IWA World Water Congress by UDC on September 13, 2022 in Copenhagen (Denmark). The session aimed to investigate issues that may impact water utilities as they move towards a more data driven world, where evidence will be essential to justify action and improve UDS performance. The workshop investigated three issues arising from new data collection, storage and analysis capabilities: (i) data quality and assurance of big data, (ii) the use of data enhance performance and ensure compliance, (iii) the dangers and opportunities to society from "open data" approaches.
- Co-UDlabs Webinar on "Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR) chemical mapping", organized by AAU on September 21, 2022 (online);
- Co-UDlabs Workshop on "Capacity problems and flow rate determination in pressurized systems", organized by Deltares on November 17, 2022 (online);
- Co-UDlabs Webinar on the principles and applications of acoustic backscattering to monitor suspended solids in natural and engineered systems organized by Eawag on May 16, 2023;
- Co-UDlabs Webinar on "Routine Uncertainty Assessment", organized by INSA and Deltares on June 12, 2023 (online);
- Co-UDlabs Webinar to present the 2nd Co-UDlabs call on Transnational Access on June 20, 2023 (online);
- Co-UDlabs Workshop to launch the 2nd TA call during the Novatech 2023 conference taking place in July 2023 in Lyon (France);
- Co-UDlabs Hackathon for participants in the 2nd TA call to connect, team up, share ideas and discuss early proposals, on September 6, 2023.
- Co-UDlabs Workshop on Uncertainty assessment in UD monitoring data (in French) to present the UDMT toolbox to a technical audience, on October 10, 2023 in Lyon (France).

- Co-UDlabs UDMT Workshop at the 7th edition of the Spanish Water Engineering Days (VII Jornadas de Ingeniería del Agua, JIA) on October 18, 2023 in Cartagena (Spain).
- Co-UDlabs Workshop on Uncertainty assessment in UD monitoring data, organized by GRAIE and INSA on March 6-7, 2024
- Co-UDlabs Webinar on Optical and computer vision techniques for flow and processes measurements, organized by UDC and Deltares on March 15, 2024.
- INSA Lyon organised a training on metrology with the UDMT software during the 104th ASTEE congress in Toulouse, FR on June 2-4, 2024
- UDC hosted two Open Days at the Centre for Technological Innovation in Construction and Civil Engineering (CITEEC) laboratories on June 19-20, 2024 to show to early-stage researchers, school pupils, and youth how impactful research can be on water management, resilience, and sustainability in our own cities and territories
- Co-UDlabs organised a course for urban drainage practitioners, regulators, and utilities interested in monitoring the main hydraulic and water quality parameters of sewers and drainage networks on July 16-19, 2024 at the CITEEC laboratories, University of A Coruña, Spain. Participants were able to access and discover CITEEC's STREET and BLOCK experimental facilities.
- An open door day was organised by EAWAG where they present Co-UDlabs project to layman audience. This presentation took place on September 14, 2024
- A workshop was organised during the 9th edition of EURO-SAM by University of Sheffield and INSA Lyon. This workshop took place in Sheffield on September 17-18, 2024
- Co-UDlabs organised a seminar for post-PhD on opportunities in Urban drainage on September 19, 2024
- Co-UDlabs organised a online workshop for the PhD students interested in Sewer processes at Aalborg University on October 7-11, 2024 at Aalborg University, Denmark.
- INSA Lyon organised a professional training course on Uncertainty Assessment with UDMT on December 2-3, 2024 at Puy en Velay, France.
- On January 10, 2025, INSA Lyon and GRAIE organised a webinar on the Routine data validation in urban drainage with UDMT
- An online workshop on FAIR monitoring data practices in urban drainage was organised by Co-UDLabs partners and the International working group of data and models on January 28, 2025
- A webinar was organised by University of Sheffield and IKT on January 30, 2025. The topic as the techniques for monitoring underground infrastructures
- An online workshop on the key finding from Co-UDlabs was organised on March 11, 2025 by IKT.

Annex 3: External events attended by Co-UDlabs project partners

□ 19 scientific conferences:

- A poster presentation by EAWAG at Aqua Urbanica 2021 "Schwammstadt" - German speaking Urban Drainage community on 13-15 September 2021, Innsbruck (Austria);
- An oral presentation by INSA at the **POLLUTEC conference** on October 12-15, 2021, Lyon (France).
- An oral presentation by UDC at the **GW4 WSA Seminar Series** of the GW4 Water Security Alliance on May 26, 2022 (online);
- An oral presentation by UDC during the IAHR Institute Meetings (part of the **39th World Congress of IAHR**) on June 19-25, 2022 in Grenada (Spain), and two oral presentations by UDC and UDC-EAWAG;
- An oral presentation by UDC at the **Water Innovation Europe 2022** (NBS working group event) on June 23, 2022;
- Oral presentations by USFD and EAWAG at the 10th **International Conference on Sewer Processes and Networks (SPN)** on August 23-25, 2022 in Graz (Austria);
- An oral presentation by UFSD, UDC and IKT and discussion on future research directions at the **Symposium on Urban Flooding Experiments** on September 1-2, 2022 in Lyon (France);
- An oral presentation by IKT at the **Water Networking Event "Water in an international context 2022"** on November 8, 2022, Mülheim (Germany)
- A poster presentation by Eawag at the **Aqua Urbanica 2022 "Grün statt Grau"** - German speaking Urban Drainage community on November 13-15, 2022, Glattfelden (Switzerland)
- A Keynote to the **3rd IAHR Young Water Professionals Conference 2022** on 'Managing ageing urban drainage systems, challenges and opportunities' where Co-UDlabs and other similar projects (QUICS and CENTAUR) were presented by USFD - November 29, 2022, online.
- Two presentations by IKT at the **EUR-SAM** (Sewer Assesment Management Workshop held at Lulea University (Sweden) on 15-16th February 2023, (i) A deep learning based framework for automated detection of in-pipe defects in CCTV sewer survey, (ii) Machine learning for prediction of failures in sewer networks.
- Two oral presentations by UFSD with EAWAG, INSA at the **NOVATECH 2023 Conference** on July 3-4, 2023 in Lyon (France)
- Oral presentation on "Annular Flume Studies to test the effect on antibiotic resistant genes and use of Crispr-Cas in *E. coli* from sediments affected by sewage pollution" by USFD-UPC BarcelonaTech at the **"Modern aspects of microbiology, virology and biotechnology in wartime and post-war period"** Conference on November 15-16, 2023 in Kyiv (Ukraine).
- An oral presentation by IKT at the **Water in an international context - Climate change in North Rhine-Westfalia, Great Britain and the Commonwealth Conference** on December 13, 2023 in Gelsenkirchen (Germany), hybrid.
- Two oral presentations on "Understanding the influence of leaf litter on the water balance composition of blue-green infrastructure" (by EAWAG and UDC) and on "Improving the reproducibility and provenance of

urban drainage data and models with RENKU, a platform for sustainable data science” (by EAWAG, University of Sheffield and INSA Lyon) at the ICUD 2024 (June 9-14, 2024) in Delft, Netherlands,

- A presentation by EAWAG on “Die kontinuierliche Messung der Abwasserqualität mit Kameras – erste Erfahrungen aus Pilotversuchen” during the Aqua Urbanica 2024 on September 22, 2024 in Graz, Austria.
- A presentation by Deltares about New Ideas and the Sensor Development Process during a webinar organised by the SWIG group (UK) on April 23, 2024
- An oral presentation by IKT at the **21st European Water Association Symposium at IFAT** on May 16, 2024 in Munich, Germany.
- Poster presentation by UDC at the **EGU General Assembly** on April 28, 2025 in Vienna (Austria)

□ 16 national technical events:

- An oral presentation by UDC at the **Galicia Innovation Days – Towards Horizon Europe** on October 25-29, 2021 (online);
- An oral presentation by IKT at the **StarkRegen Congress 2021** (Heavy Rain Congress) on December 2-3, 2021 in Gelsenkirchen (Germany);
- An oral presentation by IKT at the **Göttinger Abwassertage** (Goettinger Wastewater Days) on February 15-16, 2022 (online);
- A poster presentation by GRAIE at the **Webinar France-Québec “Ville Perméable”** on 17 March 2022.
- An oral presentation by UDC at the **14th Annual Seminar of the Spanish Network of Hydraulics Laboratories** on March 29, 2022 in Barcelona (Spain);
- Oral presentation by GRAIE at **Carrefour des gestions locales de l'eau** - June 29, 2022 in Rennes (France) & online (hybrid);
- A poster presentation by UDC at the **Jornadas de la AEAS** on September 28-30, 2022 in Córdoba (Spain);
- An oral presentation by INSA and GRAIE at the **Journée d'échanges Autosurveillance des systèmes d'assainissement** on October 13, 2022 in Lyon (France);
- Participation of IKT with a small exhibition stand at the **Oldenburg Pipeline Forum** on March 30-31, 2023 in Oldenburg (Germany), where Co-UDlabs flyers were distributed to visitors;
- Participation of IKT with an exhibition stand at the **ROKATECH Kassel 2023** on May 9-12, 2023 in Kassel (Germany), where Co-UDlabs flyers were distributed to visitors;
- An oral presentation by INSA at the **Journées Techniques EPNAC 2023** on October 3, 2023 in Angoulême (France)
- An oral presentation by IKT at **Kennis - en netwerkdag Professioneel Afvalwatertransport** on December 6, 2023 in Amersfoort (The Netherlands)
- An oral presentation by USFD at the **Advances in flood modelling and forecasting event** on February 1-2, 2024 in Sheffield (UK)

- A poster presentation by IKT during the **Jubiläumsfeier "10 Jahre Johannes-Rau-Forschungsgemeinschaft"**, Mit Grußworten, Podiumsdiskussion, Begleitausstellung und Empfang (Anniversary celebration "10 years Johannes-Rau-Research Association" on April 8, 2024
- An oral presentation by IKT and INSA at the **IKT 30th anniversary event** on September 11-12, 2024 in Gelsenkirchen, Germany.
- A poster presentation by UDC at the **redSUDS conference** at the School of Civil Engineering of the University of Cantabria on April 7-8, 2025 - Santander, Spain. The presentation showcased the results of research conducted between the Universidade da Coruña and the institutes IKT (Germany) and EAWAG (Switzerland) to analyze the aging of certain sustainable drainage systems such as green roofs and porous pavements.

□ 4 exhibition booths:

- Online booth organised at the **International Conference on Research Infrastructures (ICRI 2022)** on October 19-21, 2022 in Brno (Czech Republic) – hybrid event. Co-UDlabs also co-hosted the “Long-term sustainability of small and mid-scale distributed RI projects” hybrid side event of ICRI with the VITALISE project.
- Booth organized at the **NOVATECH 2023** conference on July 3-4, 2023 in Lyon (France)
- Booth organized at ICUD 2024 on June 9-14, 2024 at Defl (Netherlands)
- Joint exhibition space with the European project D4runoff at the **redSUDS conference** at the School of Civil Engineering of the University of Cantabria on April 7-8, 2025 - Santander, Spain.

□ 6 Open science/popularization events:

- Poster presentation by UDC at the **Galician Night of Researchers** taking place at A Coruña (Spain) on September 24, 2021.
- Visit of the INSA research infrastructure and other urban drainage infrastructures for schools during the **“Fête de la Science” 2023** on October 9-13, 2023 in Villeurbanne (France).
- Presentation by USFD of **“Autonomous Sensing in Urban Drainage Systems”** on February 12, 2024 at the University of the 3rd Age association in Sheffield (UK).
- Participation of UDC in the **GNIGHT 2024 – Noite Europea das Persoas Investigadoras 2024** taking place in A Coruña, Spain on 27 September 2024.
- Participation of UDC in the EU Green Week 2024 on 19-20 June 2024 with a open-door event of its research infrastructures.
- Open Lab Day organized by EAWAG and Empa on 14 September 2024 in Dübendorf, Switzerland.

□ 7 Other events, including in collaboration with other EU-funded projects:

- Oral presentation by UDC at the **LIFE DRAINRAIN** project final event on October 20, 2022 in Ferrol (Spain) where Co-UDlabs and other projects (Life greensewers, Nice NBS) were presented.

- One panel discussion by Deltares at the **Blue planet Online conference** "Artificial Intelligence: Reshaping the Water Industry" on November 22, 2022, Berlin (Germany) and online.
- Oral presentation of UDC at the **BlueGreen Innovation Challenge Hackathon** organized by the BARCOVE project on September 14, 2023. The 'Building an Applied Research Facility Into CoVE' (BARCoVE) Erasmus+ project is about conducting applied research in VET on Urban Greening.
- UDMT presentation by INSA during a seminar at the **Delta Water Institute** on October 23, 2023 in Nanjing, China
- Oral presentation by GRAIE at an information exchange/coffee morning at **CEREMA** (France) on March 25, 2024 in Clermont Ferrand, France. Presentation of: Co-UDlabs overview, RI mapping/cataloguing goal (get involved), Data/ Protocol Harmonisation (get involved), JCUD new UDRAIN group (get involved), presentation of UDMT tool and sharing of supporting documents, discussion of the optical observation techniques being developed in Co-UDlabs.
- Participation in the **Water4All Partnership workshop on Research Infrastructures** (April 8-10, 2024 – Orleans, France) where GRAIE started discussions on possible collaboration with Co-UDlabs on mapping of Research Infrastructure and the harmonization of data and protocols.
- Presentation of findings from JRA8 (gully pot sediments monitoring) by Deltares at the **Global Webinar on Best practices and Innovations in Water Sensing of the SWIG** (Sensors for Water interest group) on April 23, 2024.

Annex 4: Co-UDlabs KPI analysis

Dissemination or communication channel	Tool	When (and where, if relevant)	Target audiences							KPI	Target M48	Results M48	Evaluation - M48				Partner(s) in charge	
			Academics and researchers	Industry / Practitioners	Government / Policy-makers	EU and international networks	National technology networks	EU projects	General public/advocacy groups				High (>100%)	Good (≤ 100%)	Moderate (≤ 75%)	Low (<50%)		
Events to be organised by the project partners	2 Early-stage researchers seminars	1) June 27-28, 2022 2) September 19-20, 2024	X								Number of participants	20	1) 33 2) 7	>20	≤ 20	≤ 15	< 10	UDC, USFD
	- 25th European Junior Scientists Workshop (EJSW) on UD monitoring	May 15-21, 2022	X								Number of participants	22	20	>22	≤ 22	≤ 16	< 11	INSA
	PhD course on Sewer Processes	2023 --> October 7-11, 2024	X								Number of participants	40	9	>40	≤ 40	≤ 30	< 20	AAU
	Industrial workshop on flow rate determination of pumping stations and hydraulic structures (1 day)	November 17, 2022		X			X				Number of participants	20	45	>20	≤ 20	≤ 15	< 10	DEL
	Uncertainty assessment in UD monitoring data (2 days)	2023--> 6-7 March 2024		X			X				Number of participants	12	8	>12	≤ 12	≤ 9	< 6	INSA
	Applied course on UD metrology (4 days)	July 16-19, 2024		X			X				Number of participants	12	21	> 12	≤ 12	≤ 9	< 6	UDC
	2 IKT-association practice workshops (2 days)	1) November 3-4, 2021 2) March 11, 2025	X	X			X				Number of participants	20	1) 59 2) 50	> 20	≤ 20	≤ 15	< 10	IKT
	Webinars and online lectures	2022 to 2025 1) September 21, 2022 2) May 16, 2023 3) June 12, 2023 4) March 15, 2024 5) January 10, 2025 6) January 30, 2025	X	X	X	X	X	X			Number of webinars	6	6	>6	≤ 6	≤ 4	< 3	IKT / all research institutions
											Number of attendees	30	1st webinar: 18 2nd webinar: 50 3rd webinar: 35 4th webinar: 25 5th webinar: 51 6th webinar: 50	>30	≤ 30	≤ 22	< 15	
	Side event at the Sewer Processes and Networks (SPN) conference	August 23, 2022 (Graz, Austria)		X		X	X				Number of participants	30	18	> 30	≤ 30	≤ 22	< 15	INSA/GRAIE
	Side event at the NOVATECH conference	July 2023 (Lyon, France)		X		X	X				Number of participants	30	49	> 30	≤ 30	≤ 22	< 15	GRAIE
	2 webinars and 2 hackathons	Before the TA calls the access to the research infrastructures	X	X		X	X				Number of attendees	60	1st webinar/hack: 100/61 2nd webinar/hack: 28/28	> 60	≤ 60	≤ 45	< 30	UDC
	2 dissemination workshops on smart governance	Side events of IWA specialized working groups conferences or meetings 1) September 13, 2022 2) January 28, 2025		X	X	X	X	X			Number of participants	30	1st workshop: 40 2nd workshop: 16	> 30	≤ 30	≤ 22	< 15	EAWAG
3 Workshops related with results of JRAs	Side events of IWA specialized working groups conferences or meetings 1) UDMT workshop - August 23, 2022 2) UDMT workshop - October 17, 2023 3) EURO-SAM workshop	X	X		X	X	X			Number of participants	40	1) 18 2) 11 3) 25	> 40	≤ 40	≤ 30	< 20	INSA, USFD, UDC	
Final Info Day	At the end of the project	X	X	X	X	X	X	X		Number of attendees	50	37	> 50	≤ 50	≤ 37	< 25	Euronovia, UDC	

Participation in external events and conferences	Scientific conferences	2022, 2023, 2024, 2025	X	X	X	X	X				Number of conferences	15	19	> 15	≤ 15	≤ 11	< 7	All research partners	
	National technical events	2022, 2023, 2024, 2025		X			X				Number of events	10	16	> 10	≤ 10	≤ 7	< 5	All partners	
	Fairs in innovation and technology related events	2022, 2023, 2024, 2025		X		X	X	X			Number of exhibitions	3	4	> 3	≤ 3	≤ 2	< 1	All partners	
	Open-science events	2022, 2023, 2024, 2025							X	X	Number of events	10	7	> 10	≤ 10	≤ 7	< 5	All partners	
Communication/dissemination material and activities	Project branding (logo, visual identity, communication templates, project leaflet, etc.)	At the beginning of the project	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	1	1	1	>1	≤ 0	-	-	-	Euronovia	
	Communication package	M6	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	1	1	1	> 1	≤ 0	-	-	-	Euronovia	
	Flyer	M6	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	Number of flyers distributed	2000	1200	> 2000	≤ 2000	≤ 1500	< 1000	-	Euronovia	
	Brochure	M24	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	Number of brochures distributed	2000	1200	> 2000	≤ 2000	≤ 1500	< 1000	-	Euronovia	
	Newsletter	Every 6 months, starting M6	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	Number of issues	8	14	> 8	≤ 8	≤ 6	< 4	-	Euronovia
											Number of subscribers	100	546	> 100	≤ 100	≤ 75	< 50	-	Euronovia
	Press release	At the start and at the end of the project	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	Number of press releases	2	3	> 2	≤ 2	≤ 1	< 0	-	Euronovia
	Articles in specialized magazines	Whole project duration	X	X		X	X				Number of articles	2	2	>2	≤ 2	≤ 1	< 0	-	All partners
	Timeline infography	At the end of the project	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	Number of infography	1	2	> 1	≤ 1	≤ 0	-	-	Euronovia
	1 Motion design video	September 2022	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	Number of views on Youtube	500	382	> 500	≤ 500	≤ 375	< 250	-	Euronovia
	Website	Whole project duration	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	Number of visits	100/month	443/month	> 100	≤ 100	≤ 75	< 50	-	Euronovia
											Number of news	1 news/month = 48	99	> 48	≤ 48	≤ 36	< 24	-	Euronovia
	LinkedIn page	Whole project duration	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	Number of members	200	652	> 200	≤ 200	≤ 75	< 100	-	All (leader: Euronovia)
											Number of posts	1/month = 48	182	>48	≤ 48	≤ 36	< 24	-	Euronovia
	Twitter account	Whole project duration	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	Number of followers	200	217	> 200	≤ 200	≤ 75	< 100	-	All (leader: Euronovia)
											Number of tweets	1/week= 208	315	> 208	≤ 208	≤ 156	< 104	-	Euronovia
Youtube channel with videos and interviews	from M12	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	Number of videos	15	26	> 15	≤ 15	≤ 11	< 7	-	All (leaders: Deltares/IKT)	
										Number of views	7500	1617	> 7500	≤ 7500	≤ 5625	< 3750	-	Euronovia	
Media press kit	M24 and M48	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	Number of press kit	2	2	>2	≤ 2	≤ 1	< 0	-	Euronovia	
Public relations and media coverage	Whole project duration			X	X	X	X	X	X	Number of external articles in the media	15	22	>15	≤ 15	≤ 11	< 7	-	All partners	
Publications	Scientific publications (peer-reviewed research papers) and related datasets	From 2022	X	X						Nber of scientific papers	10	11	>10	≤ 10	≤ 7	< 5	-	All research partners	
										Nber of datasets	20	27	>20	≤ 20	≤ 15	< 10	-		
										Number of visits / downloads of data-sets on Zenodo	3000	6831	>3000	≤ 3000	≤ 2250	≤ 1500	-		
	Technical articles (international and national journals)	From 2022		X		X	X				Nber of technical papers	8	3	>8	≤ 8	< 6	< 4	-	All research partners
Conference proceedings	From 2022	X	X		X	X				Nber of conference papers	15	28	>15	≤ 15	≤ 11	< 7	-	All research partners	
Tot. KPI M48											44								
													26	8	6	4			
													59%	18%	14%	9%			

Annex 5: Lean Canvas of Co-UDlabs KERs

KER1 – Prototype of a non-contact water quality monitoring device

1) Problem

Top 3 problems

Explain: **What** is the problem and **why** is it a problem.

Additionally, attempt to add numbers or quantifiable measures that will clearly highlight the scale of the problem.

The primary challenge we are addressing revolves around the absence of key capabilities in the current tools available to potential users to continuously monitor the quality of their wastewater. At present, these users lack the ability to obtain real-time continuous measurements of water quality (resolution of minutes), monitor pollutant time series, and employ maintenance-free and non-contact methodologies in their combined sewers, storm sewers and wastewater treatment plants.

The top 3 specific problems are:

1. Lack of Real-Time, High-Resolution Water Quality Data

What is the problem?

Most existing systems do not provide continuous, real-time measurements of water quality at high temporal resolution (e.g., per minute).

Why is this a problem?

Without minute-scale data, sudden pollutant surges (e.g., from combined sewer overflows or industrial discharges) go unnoticed, leading to mismanagement at wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs).

Quantifiable impact:

We estimate that over 50% of pollutant loads in urban runoff events can occur in the first 30 minutes ("first flush"), yet conventional sampling often misses this window. Typical grab sampling intervals (1–2 hours or more) fail to capture these short-term dynamics.

2. No Maintenance-Free, Non-Contact Solutions

What is the problem?

Current water quality sensors require contact with water and frequent maintenance (e.g., cleaning fouled probes), especially in harsh environments like sewers.

Why is this a problem?

Manual cleaning and recalibration are labour-intensive and expensive. Sensor fouling also leads to incorrect readings, making the data unreliable.

Quantifiable impact:

Sensor maintenance can represent 20–30% of operating costs in long-term monitoring programs. In combined sewer environments, biofouling can degrade sensor performance within 2–5 days in extreme cases a couple of hours.

3. Inability to Monitor Pollutant Time Series

What is the problem?

Many utilities lack tools to generate continuous time series of pollutant indicators (e.g., turbidity, COD, ammonium), especially in dynamic flow conditions.

Why is this a problem?

Without time series, it is difficult to identify pollution trends, plan operational responses, or comply with regulatory reporting on discharges.

Quantifiable impact:

Up to 80% of regulatory exceedances in WWTPs are linked to undetected short-term load peaks. Continuous data can reduce compliance-related penalties and treatment inefficiencies.

Other problems we identified are:

- Inadequacy of current technologies in delivering a holistic and user-friendly approach for water quality assessment.
- Conventional instruments fall short in providing an integrated solution for open channels (flow and pollution from a single sensor).

2) Existing alternatives to address the same problems

Indicate how these problems are solved today.

The prevailing instruments, such of **ion-selective electrodes (ISE)** fall short in offering a comprehensive solution that caters to the specific needs of users. ISE measures ammonium and it requires 1-2h per week of maintenance, absolute measurement quality is very questionable.

Another attractive option for operational water quality monitoring capabilities is the use of **Submerged UV-VIS Spectrometer Probes**.

Characteristics:

- Developed for near real-time measurements.
- Examples include Spectrolyser, GoSYS Blue probe, etc.
- Offer high-resolution measurements, multiparameter analysis, and medium maintenance.
- Monitoring principle is correlation-based.
- Adjusted to the local wastewater matrix.
- Minimum of 20-40 reference samples recommended for reliable calibration (Caradot et al., 2013).

For precise measurements, **wet chemical analysers** are used.

Characteristics:

- Deploy chemical reactions and spectrophotometry.
- Provide measurements of specific water quality parameters in wastewater every 15-30 minutes.
- Utilize pre-treatment steps like filtration and colorimetric measurements.
- Can measure a wide range of pollutants, including ammonium, nitrate, phosphate, and organic matter.
- Cost exceeds >45k CHF, limiting widespread usage.
- State of the Art for Online Monitoring.

However, all the existing solutions have the following limitations:

- Expensive.
- Chemical consumption.
- Maintenance efforts.
- Limited monitoring quality (drift, trueness, precision, ...)

3) Customer segment

*Identify who has the problem, define target customers. Distinguish between users and customers (customers buy, users “use”)
Be clear on explaining the geographic location of your customers, the industry in which they are operating in, as well as connecting them to the problem in question.*

We aim to create a versatile instrument with widespread applicability and target a diverse range of potential interested users, including, wastewater treatment plant operators, sewer system managers, monitoring companies, consultant engineers, service providers. Also, research institutes, regulatory authorities, and NGOs will be interested in our product, possibly even chemical, food, and pharmaceutical industries. We are already in contact with interested users in Europe, Canada and the U.S.A, but the next trials are planned in Switzerland, France, and potentially in Germany.

4) Early adopters

Who are they? What is your relation to them? etc.

Explain the geographic location, connect them to the problem, explain exactly why these will be the first adopters, clarify your current connection to them etc.

Our early adopters are primarily wastewater treatment plant (WWTP) operators and sewer utilities that face significant challenges in real-time, high-resolution monitoring of influent water quality. These organizations are actively looking for innovative, non-contact, and maintenance-free solutions that can improve operational performance and regulatory compliance.

Current and Planned Deployments

Wastewater Treatment Plant Operators (Switzerland & France):

AV Altenrhein, Entsorgung + Recycling Zürich, and Zentraler Abwasserverband Olten are already engaged in pilot deployments. These utilities are based in Switzerland, where strict environmental standards and complex hydraulic conditions make early detection of pollution events a top priority.

SUEZ is involved in testing the system in WWTP Mulhouse (France), a large-scale facility serving a mixed urban-industrial area. The goal is to better manage inflow loads during storm events and industrial discharges.

These utilities are directly connected to the problem of lacking high-frequency, non-invasive monitoring tools. They have all expressed interest or are already hosting deployments, and we are in regular contact through existing collaborative research projects and technology evaluation partnerships.

Planned Deployments with Sewer Utilities

Emschergenossenschaft (Germany) and Aquafin (Belgium) have expressed interest in trialing the system for stormwater event monitoring and overflow characterization. Both operate extensive combined sewer systems and are actively seeking digital tools to improve predictive maintenance and regulatory reporting.

Engagement with these utilities has started through joint discussions in our personal network, at IWA events and technical workshops, and we plan pilot deployments within the next project phase.

Industry Partners and Commercial Interest

We also plan to enter in dialogue with technology integrators and sensor manufacturers who see value in adopting or integrating our solution into their product portfolios:

XYLEM: Interest in complementing their existing monitoring suite with non-contact optical tools.

Unimon (CH), Stebatec (CH), and Nivus (DE): All active in sewer monitoring and automation, and exploring co-development and resale opportunities.

These companies are strategically located in Central Europe and have existing customer networks aligned with the target use cases of our system. We are in early-stage business development discussions, supported by shared pilots or NDAs in preparation.

Why These Are the First Adopters

- They operate under high regulatory pressure to document inflow dynamics and CSO behavior.
- They manage complex infrastructure where manual monitoring is inefficient and current sensor technology often fails.
- They already have technical competence and organizational incentives to adopt cutting-edge digital tools.
- We have existing relationships via R&D partnerships, field deployments in past project, and participation in innovation-consortia like Co-UDLabs and RICHI (Swiss R&D project).

5) Unique Value proposition

*Why are you different and worth buying? Explain the **uniqueness** of your solution.*

Provide facts and data, explaining the performance of your product compared to alternative solutions (efficiency increase of 20%, decreased energy consumption of 10%, 30% fewer development costs, etc.).

- Very little maintenance
- High temporal resolutions
- Flow and water quality in a single device
- Low power consumption
- Possibility for spectral fingerprinting, delta-change of wastewater
- Can analyse composition changes by analysis of the spectra
- Could potentially be adjusted/customized for many different applications => classify spectrum according to your needs

6) Solutions

Top 3 features of your solution and how it differentiates you from competitors.

Be sure to explain the format of your solution (is it a machine, equipment, software, service, process, etc.), what it does, and how it does it.

The “PollutionKeeper” system will be an advanced, non-invasive intelligent optical imaging device that monitors water flow and pollutant levels such as total suspended, organics, and nutrients with good accuracy in harsh wastewater conditions. This device works quickly and efficiently to provide water quality data in a timely manner. [we do not know the accuracy. Probably differs depending on the installation and the environment]. The unique selling proposition is the combined measurement of flow and water quality with virtual no maintenance, which is not possible today.

7) Unfair Advantage

What is it that gives you an advantage in front of the competition? Something that can't be easily copied or bought.

This could be IPR, being first movers on new technology that takes years to develop etc. Be sure to explain why the listed points provide you with an advantage.

Our unfair advantage lies in a combination of technological maturity, intellectual know-how, and strategic positioning that cannot be easily replicated or bought by competitors.

1. First-Mover on Multispectral, Non-Contact Water Monitoring in Open Channels

We are the first to combine multispectral optical imaging with hydraulic sensing in a single non-contact device specifically designed for wastewater and sewer environments. This field is notoriously harsh, where most optical

technologies fail — and developing a solution that works reliably here, especially with UV-LED lighting, takes years of domain-specific expertise, calibration data, and validation trials.

2. Proprietary Spectral Processing and Classification Framework

Our system not only captures images, it translates spectral data into actionable pollutant information using a custom machine-learning pipeline. We are building a unique dataset of wastewater spectral signatures tied to pollutant dynamics — something that competitors cannot replicate without similar access to infrastructure, domain knowledge, and years of empirical data.

3. Deep Integration into Real-World Water Utilities & Research Networks

Through collaborations with major utilities (e.g., SUEZ, Zurich ERZ, AV Altenrhein), and our involvement in initiatives like Co-UDLabs and UDRAIN, we have early access to pilot infrastructure, user feedback loops, and credibility within the water tech community.

8) Channels

How will you reach your customers/early adopters? How do you deliver/promote value?

To reach our early adopters, we are partnering with utilities and industrial stakeholders who are already purchasing prototypes and providing feedback to tailor the system to real-world use cases. We actively present the PollutionKeeper solution to wastewater utilities, monitoring companies, and engineering firms, supported by clear marketing materials and case studies. Participation in leading trade fairs like IFAT will further boost visibility and engagement.

Our value lies in reducing maintenance costs through non-contact design and delivering high-resolution pollutant time series that support smarter, data-driven water management. Possibly, we will boost value creation by partnering with process control specialists, which could then offer a turn-key solution that saves operational cost, e.g. by reducing blower energy consumption (major cost factor at municipal WWTPs).

9) Key Metrics

Key aspects/activities you need to measure to track the success (e.g. units sold, users registered, retaining users, paying customers, number of complaints ...)

To track the success of the PollutionKeeper system, we plan to track two main key performance indicators. These include the number of devices sold, with targets of 10 units in year 1 and 30 units in year 2, and participation in major trade fairs such as IFAT to increase market visibility. Additional metrics might include the number of developing customers onboard, and the frequency of product support requests — although this needs refinement depending on the type of customer (primary or secondary use). Retention of early adopters could also serve as a strong indicator of product-market fit.

10) Revenue Streams

The main revenue streams will come from the sale of PollutionKeeper devices and associated services (camera + AI + web-frontend and user interface+ data portal), which are a follow-up achievement resulting from the exploitable result PollutionKeeper proposal(project). Thus, the company who will exploit the result is external to the consortium and does not wish to publicly provide revenue streams at this stage.

11) Cost structure

Which will be the main costs when the solution is ready for the market? Prototyping, HR costs, Eng. costs, MFG costs, marketing costs etc. Estimate costs for each "cost-entity". Estimate costs after seed stage 6 months and 3 years.

Primary costs for bringing the PollutionKeeper camera to market will include personnel, hardware prototyping and manufacturing, engineering and R&D, and go-to-market activities. We estimate around 300k € costs after 6-month seed stage, and 2000k after 3 years.

KER2 – Strategic agenda on urban drainage research infrastructures - UDRAIN

1) Problem

Top 3 problems

Explain: **What** is the problem and **why** is it a problem.

Additionally, attempt to add numbers or quantifiable measures that will clearly highlight the scale of the problem.

Urban drainage innovation depends heavily on large-scale research infrastructures where technologies can be tested under real-world conditions. However, many of these RIs have traditionally operated in isolation, with limited visibility and fragmented efforts.

Main problems:

- 1) Research infrastructures are not organised to be easily accessible to other researchers and industrial developers.
- 2) There is often a lack of awareness of available RI in relevant universities, water utilities and their supply chain, especially at a transnational level.
- 3) Practitioners and scientists work with different timescales (fast solutions vs well-based solutions) and with different standards and datasets: there is a lack of harmonisation of FAIR data and protocols.

This has hindered the effective transfer of knowledge and slowed down the adoption of novel, sustainable drainage solutions by practitioners and water utilities.

2) Existing alternatives to address the same problems

Indicate how these problems are solved today.

There are no real existing alternatives, except through some punctual international and national collaborations in which different institutions team up to share their research infrastructures for a limited period. Mostly, researchers in the field of Urban Drainage do research alone, working in silos at different levels: among different actors and different countries, with limited sharing of outcomes.

3) Customer segment

Identify who has the problem, define target customers. Distinguish between users and customers (customers buy, users “use”)

Be clear on explaining the geographic location of your customers, the industry in which they are operating in, as well as connecting them to the problem in question.

- The users of the Research Infrastructures will be Suppliers, Designers, Research Organizations from Europe, North America and Australia at first approach
- The customers of the Research Infrastructures will be the Water operators and Wastewater Associations, and researcher institution if they have own funding to attend to the facilities.
- There are two approach levels to the customers and users: international (e.g. EU) and national level. This approach can be done by means of the different international wastewater associations which are formed by national wastewater operators and associations.

4) Early adopters

Who are they? What is your relation to them? etc.

Explain the geographic location, connect them to the problem, explain exactly why these will be the first adopters, clarify your current connection to them etc.

The early adopters of the Urban Drainage RI network are the TNA users from Co-UDlabs (mainly from EU countries), the international academic community and the national professional associations which are linked with international professional associations.

5) Unique Value proposition

*Why are you different and worth buying? Explain the **uniqueness** of your solution.*

Provide facts and data, explaining the performance of your product compared to alternative solutions (efficiency increase of 20%, decreased energy consumption of 10%, 30% fewer development costs, etc.).

UDRAIN offers a collaborative platform to map, connect, and strengthen the world's large-scale urban drainage RIs, turning them into engines for innovation, education, and global cooperation. Services proposed:

- **Global inventory (Atlas) of large-scale RIs in urban drainage** to improve visibility, access, and collaboration (we received expressions of interest from 63 institutions across 30 countries within just a few months)
- **Technical cooperation and knowledge sharing** among RI managers, researchers, practitioners, SMEs, and regulators.
- **Facilitate transnational access to research infrastructures**, following the successful model of the Co-UDlabs project.
- **Standardise data collection, research protocols, and training activities.**
- **Foster mutual learning and innovation**, ensuring that infrastructure research supports real-world needs and societal challenges in urban drainage.

6) Solutions

Top 3 features of your solution and how it differentiates you from competitors.

Be sure to explain the format of your solution (is it a machine, equipment, software, service, process, etc.), what it does, and how it does it.

UDRAIN was officially launched at the **16th International Conference on Urban Drainage (ICUD)** in Delft on June 11, 2024. **The UDRAIN Working Group** was established as a pioneering initiative under the Joint Committee on Urban Drainage (JCUD) with the aim to build the **first global network of large Research Infrastructures (RI) focused on urban drainage systems**. UDRAIN will provide:

- Global catalogue of services, facilities and contacts. More than a marketplace, a trusted community.
- Training: EU training programme. Summer courses programme, short courses – programmes for applied science universities, adapted to national languages – important for some practitioners at some countries; seminars and short conference to bring the community together to solve – discuss practical problems, creation of working groups to promote joint activities.
- Transnational access programme for research infrastructures

7) Unfair Advantage

What is it that gives you an advantage in front of the competition? Something that can't be easily copied or bought.

This could be IPR, being first movers on new technology that takes years to develop etc. Be sure to explain why the listed points provide you with an advantage.

UDRAIN is the first Working Group established as a pioneering initiative under the Joint Committee on Urban Drainage (JCUD). It is recognized by professional and scientific networks, such as Water Europe, EWA, IWA/IAHR JCUD.

8) Channels

How will you reach your customers/early adopters?

How do you deliver/promote value?

We will promote it at field-related conferences and through the Co-UDlabs partner networks:

- The Co-UDlabs new network
- Historical partnership in urban hydrology
- Professional and scientific networks, as Water Europe, EWA, IWA/IAHR JCUD
- National professional associations linked with EU associations

9) Key Metrics

Key aspects/activities you need to measure to track the success (e.g. units sold, users registered, retaining users, paying customers, number of complaints ...)

- The UDRAIN working group was created. - Achieved
- 1st meeting in June at the ICUD conference - Achieved
- A map and catalogue of UDRAIN and their service offer. September 2025. The catalogue should include RIs facilities for more than 30 worldwide institutions
- Application for further funding at EU level. Infrastructure or MSCA programme 2025 – 2026.
- Development of a website for the WG. December 2025.

10) Revenue Streams

Which will be the main revenue streams when the solution is ready for the market. Explain how each of them will generate revenue and how much you expect to generate from each stream.

Estimate revenues for seed stage after 6 months and after 3 years. Quantify amounts and prices by detailing, for example, the expected number of services provided and paid, number of licenses sold at which prices etc.

- It is mainly a non-profit project
- It could be organized as a non-profit organisation, with a membership fee to get the access to the network services.
- Training. Revenues for courses fees typically could be around 10000 – 15000 € (e.g 20 people with a fee of 500 €)
- TNA to the facilities for training or research, the revenue estimation will be done using the historical financial data on TNA accesses made at Co-UDlabs

11) Cost structure

Which will be the main costs when the solution is ready for the market

Prototyping, HR costs, Eng. costs, MFG costs, marketing costs etc.

Estimate costs for each “cost-entity”. Estimate costs after seed stage 6 months and 3 years.

- A flat rate cost to establish the structure (project manager and coordination costs): 35000 € / year
- Costs related to services provision:
 - Training courses – average cost per course 10000 €
 - TNA access for research – to be estimated depending on the funding scheme (free access supported by EU funding, partially paid access)
 - Development of a pilot project between different facilities sponsored by administrations and water operators with a subscription fee to use the facilities or join the pilot project results.

KER3 – UDMT software

1) Problem

Top 3 problems

Explain: **What** is the problem and **why** is it a problem.

Additionally, attempt to add numbers or quantifiable measures that will clearly highlight the scale of the problem.

Metrology in urban drainage remains frequently of insufficient quality and best professional practices or standards are not always applied. The consequences are poor quality knowledge about the behaviour of and processes in sewers and SUDs, unreliable data about CSO discharges (both volumes and pollutant loads), and inadequate data for system compliance and performance evaluation, models calibration, planning and decision making. There is therefore a need to improve the quality of data delivered by urban drainage professionals, which is really a key issue.

2) Existing alternatives to address the same problems

Indicate how these problems are solved today.

Some consulting companies offer metrology software tools (usually proprietary tools, not freely available on the market and without public detailed specifications or access) in the field of urban drainage. Some specifications are dealing with metrology, but, as far as we know, they are less advanced than the tools we developed in the UDMT software. For example, there is no systematic account of sensor calibration in data processing and interpretation, there is no or insufficient assessment of uncertainties with non-transparent methods along the whole chain from data acquisition to data interpretation, data validation is either ignored or oversimplified. These weaknesses are mainly due to both i) no real incentives to improve metrology practices, and ii) a lack of professional skills in the field of rigorous metrology practices in the field of urban drainage, with existing but very slow progress. For example, Co-UDlabs (WP2 and WP6) has shown that CSO data were poorly reliable in several countries. In this context the UDMT software aims to show that powerful and scientifically based methods can be applied in a simple and fully transparent manner by operators if they want to improve their metrology practice.

3) Customer segment

Identify who has the problem, define target customers. Distinguish between users and customers (customers buy, users “use”)

Be clear on explaining the geographic location of your customers, the industry in which they are operating in, as well as connecting them to the problem in question.

Our goal is not to sell the product, but to contribute to improving the practice. Therefore, there are no customers but users only. These are public and private institutions in urban drainage (utilities, municipalities, operators, consulting companies, etc, mainly in European countries where e.g. the revised Urban WasteWater Treatment Directive will require reinforced efforts in monitoring and metrology in the coming years. But the UDMT software can be used anywhere, as the applied methods and algorithms are universal and not linked to any specific national or regional regulation.

4) Early adopters

Who are they? What is your relation to them? etc.

Explain the geographic location, connect them to the problem, explain exactly why these will be the first adopters, clarify your current connection to them etc.

Students (MSc, PhD) and most advanced professionals in urban drainage in any country, who recognize that improving the metrology practices in their field is necessary

5) Unique Value proposition

Why are you different and worth buying? Explain the **uniqueness** of your solution.

Provide facts and data, explaining the performance of your product compared to alternative solutions (efficiency increase of 20%, decreased energy consumption of 10%, 30% fewer development costs, etc.).

The UDMT software offers more advanced and scientifically based tools for:

- Sensor calibration functions, with various types of functions and calculation methods: not frequently used in a systematic way in observed practice (efficiency increase +75%)
- Sensor correlation functions, very rarely or even not used in observed practice (efficiency increase +90%)
- Systematic and complete uncertainty assessment of all data: very rarely done (efficiency increase +100%)
- Data validation at various levels: only basics in observed practice (efficiency increase +50%)
- Tracing experiments data processing: usually neglected (efficiency increase +90%).

Another key and rather unique aspect of the UDMT software is that all the above points are fully integrated and can be operated as a full chain of data processing (efficiency increase +100%).

6) Solutions

Top 3 features of your solution and how it differentiates you from competitors.

Be sure to explain the format of your solution (is it a machine, equipment, software, service, process, etc.), what it does, and how it does it.

The UDMT software tool aims to facilitate the application of best practices and methods in monitoring urban drainage systems. As these practices and methods are generic, they can also be applied in other domains.

The UDMT includes five blocks of functions:

1. Sensor calibration / Correlation: this block provides various methods to determine i) calibration functions (based on a data set of outputs of a sensor submitted to standards or certified values), and ii) correlation functions (based on a data set of values given by a sensor and corresponding values obtained e.g. with laboratory analyses of samples).
2. Calibration / Correlation correction: this block allows to convert raw values provided by a sensor into corrected values according to previously determined calibration or correlation functions. In addition, uncertainties in corrected values are estimated.
3. Uncertainty assessment: this block allows to apply standard methods (type A, type B, Monte Carlo) to various data sets. In addition, the variograph method is proposed to estimate uncertainties in integrated values (e.g. sums, means, etc.).
4. Data validation: this block provides a set of automated tests to help the user to validate data according to various criteria.
5. Tracing experiments: this block allows to calculate a discharge from experimental data collected during tracing experiments. Tracing experiments are useful to qualify flowmeters in urban drainage systems.

On-line version

The UDMT web app is available at: <http://vps-7bc5cf87.vps.ovh.net:9988/webapps/home/session.html?app=coudlabs>

All data files necessary to run the examples given in the UDMT user manual are available on pCloud at: <https://u.pcloud.link/publink/show?code=kZegnQVZM53qyjRJ4cHn7Pi5WzrR9HJOPL4V>.

Exe versions

In addition to the online version, the UDMT software is also available as executable applications that have been compiled for both Microsoft Windows and Apple Mac operating systems. The exe versions work similarly to the online

version described in this user manual. They can be downloaded here:

<https://u.pcloud.link/publink/show?code=kZegnQVZM53qyjRJ4cHn7Pi5WzrR9HJOPL4V>

and later installed on personal computers by the user.

7) Unfair Advantage

What is it that gives you an advantage in front of the competition? Something that can't be easily copied or bought. This could be IPR, being first movers on new technology that takes years to develop etc. Be sure to explain why the listed points provide you with an advantage.

The UDMT software tool aims to help urban drainage professionals to improve their practice, by making simple but easy to use tools freely available (online or as .exe versions), with advanced functions and a detailed user manual.

The main advantage is the capacity to simultaneously i) use advanced scientific methods and ii) make them easily usable for any user, in a transparent manner, accompanied with training examples and full access to all parameters and outputs for the most advanced users.

8) Channels

How will you reach your customers/early adopters? How do you deliver/promote value?

During the Co-UDlabs project, there were 2 webinars, 2 training courses (one French and one international) on the UDMT software, and also a number of presentations.

A paper will be submitted in April-May 2025 to the journal *Water Practice and Technology* to further disseminate information, with a detailed presentation of the UDMT software and examples of application.

In addition, a half-day training workshop on the UDMT software will be held at the French national annual congress of ASTEE in June 2025. A French translation of the *Water Practice and Technology* paper is also planned. Other dissemination / promotion events and opportunities are in preparation for the end of 2025 and 2026.

9) Key Metrics

Key aspects/activities you need to measure to track the success (e.g. units sold, users registered, retaining users, paying customers, number of complaints ...)

Number of downloads of the UDMT.

Number of training courses and number of participants

Number of use 6 months after the training sessions.

10) Revenue Streams

Which will be the main revenue streams when the solution is ready for the market. Explain how each of them will generate revenue and how much you expect to generate from each stream. Estimate revenues for seed stage after 6 months and after 3 years. Quantify amounts and prices by detailing, for example, the expected number of services provided and paid, number of licenses sold at which prices etc.

The UDMT software is already available, free for download and use. Therefore, there is no planned revenue streams, and no intention to move to a commercial product.

Some benefits could come from the training courses on the use of the tool, which could be used for some maintenance / evolution of the UDMT code.

A “users group” could be launched, and members will pay e.g. an annual fee with access to training, evolution of the product, etc. This possibility can be explored in 2025-2026.

11) Cost structure

Which will be the main costs when the solution is ready for the market. Prototyping, HR costs, Eng. costs, MFG costs, marketing costs etc. Estimate costs for each “cost-entity”. Estimate costs after seed stage 6 months and 3 years.

The UDMT software is already developed, so there are no additional future costs for the moment.

Future costs (no estimation) are linked to communication and training courses organisation.

Some courses can be free (online), but experience has shown that “in presence” courses are more useful. These courses should be paid for by participants (typically minimum 600-700 euros/day).

KER4 – Toronto Exfiltration System

1) Problem

Top 3 problems

Explain: **What** is the problem and **why** is it a problem. Additionally, attempt to add numbers or quantifiable measures that will clearly highlight the scale of the problem.

1. Draining new developments in a sustainable way that does not overload existing piped stormwater drainage systems.
2. Delivering few overflow events into receiving waters.
3. Minimizing the use of construction materials whilst providing a high level of drainage service that manages flood risk.

2) Existing alternatives to address the same problems

Indicate how these problems are solved today.

1. Conventional buried stormwater drainage pipes.
2. Use of Sustainable Urban Drainage Systems
3. Planning/development restrictions

3) Customer segment

Identify who has the problem, define target customers. Distinguish between users and customers (customers buy, users “use”) Be clear on explaining the geographic location of your customers, the industry in which they are operating in, as well as connecting them to the problem in question.

1. Water utilities or local authorities that have a legal obligation to provide effective drainage services
2. Developer wishing to develop land without existing stormwater drainage infrastructure.

4) Early adopters

Who are they? What is your relation to them? etc.

Explain the geographic location, connect them to the problem, explain exactly why these will be the first adopters, clarify your current connection to them etc.

1. Water utilities
2. Design consultancies supporting water utilities and developers.

5) Unique Value proposition

Why are you different and worth buying? Explain the **uniqueness** of your solution.

Provide facts and data, explaining the performance of your product compared to alternative solutions (efficiency increase of 20%, decreased energy consumption of 10%, 30% fewer development costs, etc.).

The UVP is that the Toronto Exfiltration system can provide significantly more drainage capacity (as there is now an additional exfiltration loss) at only 5% extra cost compared to a lower capacity conventional system. It can provide this additional drainage capacity without the use of value land (needed for SuDs) and with no additional need for construction materials compared to a conventional system.

6) Solutions

Top 3 features of your solution and how it differentiates you from competitors.

Be sure to explain the format of your solution (is it a machine, equipment, software, service, process, etc.), what it does, and how it does it.

1. Enhanced exfiltration from pipes – infiltration to soil.

2. Lower carbon emissions and cost compared to SuDs and traditional network enhancements to increase flow capacity.

7) Unfair Advantage

What is it that gives you an advantage in front of the competition? Something that can't be easily copied or bought. This could be IPR, being first movers on new technology that takes years to develop etc. Be sure to explain why the listed points provide you with an advantage.

1. Lower cost and land area requirement
2. First mover advantage
3. Uses traditional pipes/construction components, so no large funds are needed for product development
4. System can be incorporated into existing design codes and software packages.

8) Channels

*How will you reach your customers/early adopters?
How do you deliver/promote value?*

1. Civil engineering design consultancies

9) Key Metrics

Key aspects/activities you need to measure to track the success (e.g. units sold, users registered, retaining users, paying customers, number of complaints ...)

1. Numbers of kms constructed.
2. Numbers of water utilities willing to adopt/accept such systems.

10) Revenue Streams

Which will be the main revenue streams when the solution is ready for the market. Explain how each of them will generate revenue and how much you expect to generate from each stream.

Estimate revenues for seed stage after 6 months and after 3 years. Quantify amounts and prices by detailing, for example, the expected number of services provided and paid, number of licenses sold at which prices etc.

1. No explicit revenue streams
2. Societal benefit, more sustainable drainage system if adopted
3. Allow marginal land to be developed as flood risk is reduced at lower costs than conventional piped solution.
4. Better flood risk reduction at a lower cost.

11) Cost structure

*Which will be the main costs when the solution is ready for the market
Prototyping, HR costs, Eng. costs, MFG costs, marketing costs etc.*

Estimate costs for each "cost-entity". Estimate costs after seed stage 6 months and 3 years.

1. Production of design guidance
2. Awareness raising
3. Need to encourage adoption in building/construction codes.

KER5 – Tekno-soil design for infiltration-based SUDS

1) Problem

Top 3 problems

*Explain: **What** is the problem and **why** is it a problem.*

Additionally, attempt to add numbers or quantifiable measures that will clearly highlight the scale of the problem.

Over 70% of Europe’s population lives in urban areas, where impermeable surfaces increase the risk of flooding and pollution. Current flood management in the EU is conventional and centralized, but this approach is becoming increasingly ineffective. A promising alternative is Sustainable Drainage Systems (SUDS), which mimic natural processes based local retention, evaporation and infiltration to manage floods. However, stormwater contains chemicals and pollutants from the urban surfaces, which prone a potential risk to the groundwater when infiltrated.

The design approach for infiltration-based SUDS for local stormwater management faces the following challenges:

1. Design of Sustainable Urban Drainage Systems (SUDS) based on water infiltration into urban soils is mainly based on black box modelling without sufficient process knowledge.
2. Ensuring adequate water infiltration capacity to prevent flooding, while still allowing enough residence time to retain and remove urban chemicals, makes SuDS design very challenging.
3. The necessary parameters for correct design require costly, time-consuming measurements with specialized measurements set-ups only available at research institutions.

2) Existing alternatives to address the same problems

Indicate how these problems are solved today.

Typically, when designing Sustainable Drainage Systems (SuDS), the chemical transport and fate processes are often neglected or overlooked. In these cases, the primary focus is usually placed on managing stormwater flow and volume, with less consideration given to the potential contaminants in the water and how they move and degrade within the system. As a result, the design process may not fully account for the impacts that stormwater runoff can have on both the environment and local groundwater quality.

However, when chemical transport and fate processes are taken into account, the design approach often relies on rule-of-thumb parameter estimates and overly simplified models. These methods, while practical, may fail to accurately represent the complex interactions between pollutants, the soil, and water, leading to incomplete or less effective solutions for long-term stormwater management.

3) Customer segment

Identify who has the problem, define target customers. Distinguish between users and customers (customers buy, users “use”)

Be clear on explaining the geographic location of your customers, the industry in which they are operating in, as well as connecting them to the problem in question.

Customers include urban drainage managers responsible for stormwater management across Europe, municipal governments, water companies, and associated consulting companies. These stakeholders face challenges due to insufficient SUDS design tools, where unclear parameter inputs complicate the design process and make it difficult to establish accurate design requirements.

The primary users who will benefit are citizens (typically the customers of water companies), as poorly designed SUDS systems can increase the risk of flooding and/or lead to undesirable environmental pollution.

EPAs and water authorities will also benefit, as incorrect SUDS designs can increase the risk of chemical leaching into groundwater and other water bodies, posing significant environmental threats. Recognized best-practice design tools are essential for standardizing and enforcing the performance requirements for SUDS systems.

4) Early adopters

Who are they? What is your relation to them? etc.

Explain the geographic location, connect them to the problem, explain exactly why these will be the first adopters, clarify your current connection to them etc.

Early adopters of our solutions include municipal governments, consulting companies, and water utility companies. These stakeholders are actively engaged in addressing urban water management challenges and are motivated to implement innovative, precise, and cost-effective SUDS solutions. Their primary drivers include regulatory compliance, budgetary constraints, and concerns about public safety.

Municipal governments in urban areas frequently encounter challenges related to stormwater management and contamination. Effective SUDS are essential for compliance with environmental regulations, mitigating flooding risks, and ensuring public safety.

Consulting companies, primarily operating in developed urban centers, play a critical role in designing SUDS. They rely on accurate and reliable tools to enhance the quality and effectiveness of their consulting services.

Water companies are responsible for urban water management, ensuring the sustainable operation and maintenance of drainage systems. They operate in regions where efficient water management is vital for public health and environmental protection.

We primarily collaborate with Danish water companies and their consultants on research and development projects addressing technical and operational challenges in water management. These partnerships are built on a foundation of collaboration, mutual knowledge exchange, and joint problem-solving efforts.

5) Unique Value proposition

*Why are you different and worth buying? Explain the **uniqueness** of your solution.*

Provide facts and data, explaining the performance of your product compared to alternative solutions (efficiency increase of 20%, decreased energy consumption of 10%, 30% fewer development costs, etc.).

Our solution for the design of Sustainable Urban Drainage Systems (SUDS) is unique because it combines process-based modeling, a cost-efficient design process, and accessibility, offering a transformative approach to urban water management.

Unlike conventional “black box” models or overly simplified design tools, our approach integrates advanced hydrological modeling by incorporating site-specific infiltration characteristics and pollutant-specific transport processes.

The design approach includes a prediction of the system’s pollutant protection lifetime, enabling a balanced assessment of overall design costs in relation to the desired operational lifespan of the SuDS installation.

While construction costs are not expected to be significantly reduced, the added value lies in the system’s improved long-term performance, reliability, and environmental protection.

The method is both scientifically grounded and practical, significantly reducing the need for costly and time-consuming site-specific testing. This ensures added value without incurring additional implementation costs.

6) Solutions

Top 3 features of your solution and how it differentiates you from competitors.

Be sure to explain the format of your solution (is it a machine, equipment, software, service, process, etc.), what it does, and how it does it.

The potential outcome is a user-friendly software with guidelines, making high-performance SUDS design accessible with limited specialized expertise.

1. Relevant water flow and chemical transport processes are included in tekno-soil design.
2. A simple numerical model (MMS) allows for a both dynamic and rapid design calculation, which also facilitates inclusion of geostatistics (parameter variations and uncertainty) in the design
3. Key water flow and chemical transport parameters that are normally difficult, complicated, and expensive to measure are instead obtained from robust and verified pedotransfer functions using relatively inexpensive parameters like soil texture and organic matter content.

7) Unfair Advantage

What is it that gives you an advantage in front of the competition? Something that can't be easily copied or bought. This could be IPR, being first movers on new technology that takes years to develop etc. Be sure to explain why the listed points provide you with an advantage.

Our unfair advantage lies in the integration of scientifically grounded, process-based modeling into an accessible and cost-efficient design tool, something that is currently unavailable in the market. While most state-of-the-art SUDS design approaches rely on either oversimplified “black box” models or costly, site-specific testing, our method uniquely bridges the gap between scientific accuracy and practical usability. Compared to the current state-of-the-art, which primarily focuses on managing stormwater volume with little regard for chemical leaching risks and relies heavily on empirical models, our solution delivers a next-generation design support tool. It enables users to balance performance, cost, and environmental protection from the start of the design process, without needing costly field tests or expert-only knowledge. This combination of scientific credibility, ease of use, and real-world applicability positions our solution in front of the competition.

8) Channels

*How will you reach your customers/early adopters?
How do you deliver/promote value?*

The current state is a design concept based on scientifically grounded methodology, with the potential to be further developed into a design software tool. While it is too early to engage customers directly, it is important to establish collaborations with the early adopters, particularly water utility companies. These collaborations will focus on testing and validating the tool in real-world settings, enabling mutual learning and the refinement of the software to meet customers' needs.

In addition, these partnerships will support and facilitate pilot and full-scale demonstration projects that showcase the effectiveness and added value of the design concept and software tool.

In the longer term, customers can be reached through industry networks, professional associations, and targeted outreach to municipalities and engineering consultancies across Europe. Collaborations with water authorities will also help build credibility and promote adoption by aligning the tool with emerging standards and best practices.

9) Key Metrics

Key aspects/activities you need to measure to track the success (e.g. units sold, users registered, retaining users, paying customers, number of complaints ...)

The key activities for turning the tekno-soil design concept into a fully developed software tool involve attracting early adopters, establishing key collaborations, and seeking and securing funding for further development.

The goal of this step is to create a proof-of-concept or prototype version of the design software tool that effectively showcases the core functionalities of the design phase. Success in this phase can be measured by:

1. Establishing collaborations with at least two water utility companies that are planning SUDS installations and are willing to test the software tool during the design phase.
2. Securing funding to support the collaboration, for example through national funding programs such as Denmark's VUDP (Development and Demonstration Program for Water and Wastewater Technology).
3. Implementing at least two full-scale demonstration installations in partnership with these collaborators to validate the tool's applicability and performance in real-world conditions.
4. Developing a functional software prototype, incorporating feedback and insights gained from the demonstration installation, and tailoring the tool to meet the specific needs.

This will lay the groundwork for broader market introduction, provide proof of the tool's value in practice, and build a strong foundation for scaling across Europe.

10) Revenue Streams

Which will be the main revenue streams when the solution is ready for the market. Explain how each of them will generate revenue and how much you expect to generate from each stream.

Estimate revenues for seed stage after 6 months and after 3 years. Quantify amounts and prices by detailing, for example, the expected number of services provided and paid, number of licenses sold at which prices etc.

This is difficult to describe and predict. While licensing the software may seem like an obvious solution, the primary motivation behind the interdisciplinary development of the tekno-soil design concept is to push the technological boundaries of infiltration-based SUDS design towards better and more efficient solutions. Licensing the software could limit its spread and usage, whereas offering it as free, open-source software would likely increase its adoption, setting a technological standard for SUDS solutions and maximizing its potential for societal and environmental impact. Therefore, we believe that sharing the knowledge and the tool represents a better utilization of the investment in the larger perspective than capitalizing on it.

11) Cost structure

Which will be the main costs when the solution is ready for the market

Prototyping, HR costs, Eng. costs, MFG costs, marketing costs etc.

Estimate costs for each "cost-entity"

Estimate costs after seed stage 6 months and 3 years.

The cost of transforming the Tekno-Soil concept into a final, ready-to-use software tool is expected to require 8-12 months of software development, along with 2-3 pilot and/or full-scale demonstrations to validate the tool's applicability and performance. The associated costs are estimated to range between €200,000 and €250,000.

KER6 – Creation of new services or products on data management, buried assets evaluation and rehabilitation

1) Problem

Top 3 problems

Explain: **What** is the problem and **why** is it a problem.

Additionally, attempt to add numbers or quantifiable measures that will clearly highlight the scale of the problem.

1. Providing additional stormwater capacity to land zoned for new development.
2. Providing stormwater infrastructure to reduce flood risk, that is lower cost than traditional drainage solutions and does not impact on local receiving waters.
3. To provide a solution to reduce intermittent stormwater spills.

2) Existing alternatives to address the same problems

Indicate how these problems are solved today.

1. Traditional buried pipe networks.
2. Provision of Sustainable Urban Drainage solutions (SuDs).

3) Customer segment

Identify who has the problem, define target customers. Distinguish between users and customers (customers buy, users “use”)

Be clear on explaining the geographic location of your customers, the industry in which they are operating in, as well as connecting them with the problem in question.

Customers

1. Developers
2. Water utilities

Users

1. Public who use/buy into new developments

4) Early adopters

Who are they? What is your relation to them? etc.

Explain the geographic location, connect them to the problem, explain exactly why these will be the first adopters, clarify your current connection to them etc.

1. Water utilities that need to enhance their existing stormwater drainage infrastructure.
2. Developers that wish to drain land that they wish to develop
3. Engineering consultancies that wish to provide new design services.

5) Unique Value proposition

Why are you different and worth buying? Explain the **uniqueness** of your solution.

Provide facts and data, explaining the performance of your product compared to alternative solutions (efficiency increase of 20%, decreased energy consumption of 10%, 30% fewer development costs, etc.).

The UVP is that the Toronto Exfiltration system can provide significantly more drainage capacity (as there is now an additional exfiltration loss) at only 5% extra cost compared to a lower capacity conventional system. It can provide this additional drainage capacity without the use of valuable land (needed for SuDs) and with no additional need for construction materials compared to a conventional system. Provide facts and data, explaining the performance of your product compared to alternative solutions (efficiency increase of 20%, decreased energy consumption of 10%, 30% fewer development costs, etc.).

6) Solutions

Top 3 features of your solution and how it differentiates you from competitors.

Be sure to explain the format of your solution (is it a machine, equipment, software, service, process, etc.), what it does, and how it does it.

1. Enhanced exfiltration from pipes – infiltration to soil.
2. Lower carbon emissions and cost compared to SuDs and traditional network enhancements to increase flow capacity.
3. New design method to reduce flood risk particularly in new developments.

7) Unfair Advantage

What is it that gives you an advantage in front of the competition? Something that can't be easily copied or bought.

This could be IPR, being first movers on new technology that takes years to develop etc. Be sure to explain why the listed points provide you with an advantage.

1. Lower cost and land area requirement
2. First mover advantage
3. Uses traditional pipes/construction components, so no large funds are needed for product development
4. System can be incorporated into existing design codes and software packages.

8) Channels

How will you reach your customers/early adopters?

How do you deliver/promote value?

- Civil engineering design consultancies

9) Key Metrics

Key aspects/activities you need to measure to track the success (e.g. units sold, users registered, retaining users, paying customers, number of complaints ...)

- Numbers of kms constructed.
- Numbers of water utilities willing to adopt/accept such systems.

10) Revenue Streams

Which will be the main revenue stream when the solution is ready for the market. Explain how each of them will generate revenue and how much you expect to generate from each stream.

Estimate revenues for seed stage after 6 months and after 3 years. Quantify amounts and prices by detailing, for example, the expected number of services provided and paid, number of licenses sold at which prices etc.

- No explicit revenue streams
- Societal benefit, more sustainable drainage system if adopted
- Allow marginal land to be developed as flood risk is reduced at lower costs than conventional piped solution.
- Better flood risk reduction at a lower cost.

11) Cost structure

Which will be the main costs when the solution is ready for the market

Prototyping, HR costs, Eng. costs, MFG costs, marketing costs etc.

Estimate costs for each "cost-entity"

Estimate costs after seed stage 6 months and 3 years.

- Production of design guidance
- Awareness raising
- Need to encourage adoption in building/construction codes.

KER7– Data management toolboxes

1) Problem

Top 3 problems

Explain: **What** is the problem and **why** is it a problem.

Additionally, attempt to add numbers or quantifiable measures that will clearly highlight the scale of the problem.

-In science the need for FAIR data is widely recognized and applied, however within Urban Drainage the FAIR principles are only seldomly applied

-As there is a strong link with practice (most prominent infield laboratories) the need for data standards overarches the scientific realm and links to the data collected and managed by practitioners.

-There are no general accepted data definitions/standards for:

1/Hydraulic modelling

2/Asset management

3/Performance indicators of systems

4/monitoring data

-This situation hampers the effective/efficient use of data collected by other researchers and also is a significant hurdle in transferring findings from research into practical applications

-In the Co-UDlabs project these problems were identified, and discussed in the process asking attention for the 'data problem' in UD (in science as well as in practice).

-Existing (commercial and open access) software applied for hydrodynamic modelling, asset management, handling of monitoring data effective define the standards used in practice (and hence, to a large extent) in research projects, as a consequence many times conversion between formats is a necessity. In the process of conversion more often than not information is lost (due to different data definitions)

2) Existing alternatives to address the same problems

Indicate how these problems are solved today.

At present each research project in UD more or less defines its own data definition and management procedures (mostly founded on either national, institutional or on the software tools being used standards). Sharing and reusing data implies conversions. In 'big science' (e.g. CERN, Human genome project) the issue of data standards and data management has been addressed in great detail enabling scientist working together worldwide without too much issues with information loss as they use the same definitions, handling protocols, validation protocols and supply of Meta-data (basically in the examples mentioned the FAIR principle is applied to its full extent).

In the Netherlands a national project defining a data ontology (GWSW, see e.g.

<https://iwaponline.com/ebooks/book/920/chapter/3719608/Data-management-and-quality-control>) has been defined and is put into effect over the past ~ 10 years to come to a mutual standard for all data involved in UD.

This project has shown that it is very complicated to reach an agreement between all parties involved on virtually all aspects (definitions, formats, validation), yet the standard is set and gets applied more broadly over the past years and has triggered the development of OA software (toolboxes) to handle and convert data for practical use in a uniform manner. This project may serve as an example, however the fact that the standard aims at practitioners and is very management-oriented is considered a limitation. This is because many attributes of monitoring data, e.g. "legal entity" or "customer address" are not needed for scientific data sharing applications.

3) Customer segment

Identify who has the problem, define target customers. Distinguish between users and customers (customers buy, users "use")

Be clear on explaining the geographic location of your customers, the industry in which they are operating in, as well as connecting them with the problem in question.

All parties involved (scientists, waterboards, municipalities, industry) would benefit significantly from using the same standards for ALL data involved in UD. Being able to share data across different domains directly corresponds to the idea of EU data spaces (https://language-data-space.ec.europa.eu/help/faq/what-data-space_en#:~:text=A%20Data%20space%20is%20a,fair%20treatment%20for%20all%20involved.)

4) Early adopters

Who are they? What is your relation to them? etc.

Explain the geographic location, connect them to the problem, explain exactly why these will be the first adopters, clarify your current connection to them etc.

Early adopters would typically be researchers, utilities and large managing organizations involved in UD, but also SMEs that build data-based services (e.g. WaterZerv <https://www.inflowgo.com/>). As it is now within Co-UDlabs a toolbox has been developed to access uncertainty in monitoring data and data management plans have been drafted in the JRA along with some examples of FAIR (OA) research results (monitoring data). These examples will be used with the participants in the Co-UDlabs project and in future joint activities (education, joint follow-up projects)

5) Unique Value proposition

*Why are you different and worth buying? Explain the **uniqueness** of your solution.*

Provide facts and data, explaining the performance of your product compared to alternative solutions (efficiency increase of 20%, decreased energy consumption of 10%, 30% fewer development costs, etc.).

1. Enable cross-site and cross-project learning

FAIR data allows researchers and practitioners to compare and reuse data from different labs, cities, or time periods—without reinventing the wheel each time.

2. Reduce costs and duplication

Without FAIR standards, data is often siloed or locked in custom formats. This results in duplicated measurement campaigns, increased integration costs, or wasted time interpreting inconsistent metadata. The harmonization effort saves resources by enabling reuse, not just of data but also of methods, scripts, and workflows.

3. Support real-world applications: machine learning and compliance

FAIR data is critical if you want to:

- Train robust ML models on large, diverse datasets (e.g., predicting urban floods or CSO events)
- Benchmark system performance across utilities
- Perform compliance assessments under EU directives

4. Attract community and industry participation

FAIR data systems that generate services from open data can attract stakeholders—from scientists to regulators to industry innovators.

5. Promote trust and transparency

Standardized, well-documented data helps improve the traceability, reproducibility, and credibility of scientific and operational findings. This builds confidence in published results and supports decisions in infrastructure planning, environmental compliance, and emergency management

In short, FAIR standards are not just about better data—they're about better decisions, smarter infrastructure, and more collaborative science.

6) Solutions

Top 3 features of your solution and how it differentiates you from competitors.

Be sure to explain the format of your solution (is it a machine, equipment, software, service, process, etc.), what it does, and how it does it.

-Encourage co-operation between active research groups and frontrunning practitioners in order to arrive at general data definitions, exchange formats and data handling protocols.

-Encourage the development of (preferably OA) toolboxes for enhancing a wide application of developed data definitions

Solutions Developed in Co-UDlabs and Related Initiatives:

1. Standardized Data Collection Templates

A unified data collection template was created (based on Eawag's template) to harmonize metadata, sampling frequency, sensor setup, and units across Transnational Access (TA) and Joint Research Activities (JRA). Adjusted to address gaps in pre-publication data management (e.g., workflow diagrams, sensor specs, calibration plans).

2. Renku Workflows for Reproducible Analysis

An example of a complete workflow using Renku, enabling:

- Versioned, documented analysis pipelines for (selected) urban drainage data
- Reproducible plots comparing original publications vs re-analyses 20231031_D2.1_Data harm.
- Includes prebuilt Python/R environments for researchers.

3. Adoption of Open Standards (OGC)

- Promoted and demonstrated use of:
- Observations & Measurements (O&M) XML schemas
- SensorThings API for real-time data

4. Ontology Translation and Expansion

- Provided an English translation of the Dutch GWSW ontology.
- Identified GWSW as a starting point for an internationally recognized urban water ontology.

5. Urban Drainage Metrology Toolbox (UDMT)

A curated set of tools and guidelines to improve measurement accuracy and consistency across sites, linked with standard variable naming conventions, calibration routines, and terminology mapping

6. Harmonized Terminology and Units

Compiled and compared variable names across multiple research infrastructures (e.g., UWO, Bellinge, SIPIBEL)

7) Unfair Advantage

What is it that gives you an advantage in front of the competition? Something that can't be easily copied or bought. This could be IPR, being first movers on new technology that takes years to develop etc. Be sure to explain why the listed points provide you with an advantage.

Commercial suppliers of UD-related software could argue that (if an overall standard is developed with public money) they lose an advantage they have with existing customers, on the other hand, adapting their tools to this standard allows an easier access to potential customers. So, all in all, it is estimated that any claim for unfair advantage will fail.

The consortium's unique strength lies in its active role in shaping data standards and FAIR data practices within the urban drainage community. Building on contributions to initiatives such as Co-UDlabs, the IWA/IAHR Working Group on Data and Models (IWGDM), and national efforts like the GWSW ontology, the team offers integrated expertise in scientific data management, sensor-based monitoring, and open data infrastructures.

A key differentiator vs. commercial companies such as NIVUS or KISTERS, who offer data monitoring, management and integration services, is the consortium's development and use of open, modular toolchains—such as Renku for reproducible workflows, SensorThings API for real-time monitoring, and OGC-compliant formats like O&M XML.

These tools are designed for transparency, reuse, and long-term interoperability, enabling researchers, regulators, and infrastructure operators to build upon rather than be locked into proprietary systems. In parallel, the team's work on terminology harmonization, the Urban Drainage Metrology Toolbox (UDMT), and ontology translation is helping to define the next wave of data and interoperability standards—standards that commercial vendors will ultimately need to follow.

8) Channels

*How will you reach your customers/early adopters?
How do you deliver/promote value?*

Most important is to spread the use of standard in the scientific community, as with other results or findings from the Co-UDlabs project, we anticipate an important role her for the WG's working under the umbrella of the IWA/IAHR JCUD; more specifically the recently installed WG UDRAIN and International Working Group on Data and Models, Emerging Substances, Asset Management, Real Time control. Other targets consider international and national wastewater associations, such as EWA and DWA as well as European institutions like JRC. A first activity in this respect is scheduled by the WG UDRAIN, during the UDM conference 2025 in Innsbruck, Austria, a workshop on data management based on Co-UDlabs findings is planned, see:

https://www.uibk.ac.at/media/filer_public/81/61/8161561a-f829-4ee6-984c-6d5babd1fce5/udm_co-udlabs_workshop_submit_vf.pdf. Further a series of workshops on data models in UD and FAIR data is organized by the IWGDM in 2025: <https://co-udlabs.eu/evenements/workshop-on-fair-data-sharing-in-urban-drainage-data-models/>

9) Key Metrics

Key aspects/activities you need to measure to track the success (e.g. units sold, users registered, retaining users, paying customers, number of complaints ...)

- The number of FAIR datasets being issued
- number of OA toolboxes being developed and their application (downloads, shape and extent of the associated communities).

10) Revenue Streams

Which will be the main revenue stream when the solution is ready for the market. Explain how each of them will generate revenue and how much you expect to generate from each stream.

Estimate revenues for seed stage after 6 months and after 3 years. Quantify amounts and prices by detailing, for example, the expected number of services provided and paid, number of licenses sold at which prices etc.

As with any standard, setting and implementing a standard for UD data and data management, will benefit all involved in a manner that is very hard to express in terms of money, as we anticipate that the revenues will mainly encompass avoiding wrong designs or wrong operational decisions. In terms of scientific revenues the main revenue is found in a lot of time saved by researchers developing their own data management tools (which may take a considerable amount of the time of e.g. a PhD student, while the quality of such tools is meagre at best). A second scientific revenue is that data can be more easily being shared between groups, allowing for a more effective co-operation between groups worldwide.

11) Cost structure

N.A.

KER8 – Training content

1) Problem

Top 3 problems

Explain: **What** is the problem and **why** is it a problem.

Additionally, attempt to add numbers or quantifiable measures that will clearly highlight the scale of the problem.

- There is gap between topics addressed in academic research, in part this is due to a mismatch in the content of courses for practitioners
- Accessibility of academic output for practitioners is limited, this is mainly due to the fact that research results are mostly locked behind pay-walls.
- Scientific outputs are very mostly specialistic in nature and lack direct applicability, it is very hard for a non-initiate to identify relevant results for a practical question
- In most countries guidelines, regulations and communication are posed in the national language, where scientific publications are mostly formulated in (a kind of) English, this hampers the quick assimilation of scientific findings, but also limits the access to the scientific community to national institutes.

2) Existing alternatives to address the same problems

Indicate how these problems are solved today.

- A main method to counteract the accessibility of scientific results is Open Access publishing, which is gaining momentum in the past few years
- In many academic institutes publishing research is valued more than teaching, this causes a bias in terms of attention by academics towards research, in some countries (e.g. the Netherlands) this is slowly changing, and is resulting in open courseware
- A often overlooked method is encouraging practitioners to hold a part-time position in academia, this ensures that teachers maintain a significant link with practice, which is especially of importance for engineering studies.

3) Customer segment

Identify who has the problem, define target customers. Distinguish between users and customers (customers buy, users “use”)

Be clear on explaining the geographic location of your customers, the industry in which they are operating in, as well as connecting them with the problem in question.

The main beneficiaries of the contributions of Co-UDlabs to training content are:

- 1/regular students (B.Sc. M.Sc. and PhD level)
- 2/practitioners (public sector professional) in search for post academic education
- 3/firms (e.g. consultants, construction firms) for training of their personnel and/or identifying parties/persons that help them address specific problems and/or research topics.

4) Early adopters

Who are they? What is your relation to them? etc.

Explain the geographic location, connect them to the problem, explain exactly why these will be the first adopters, clarify your current connection to them etc.

The early adopters will most probably be persons/organizations that are already working with the partners in Co-UDlabs, within UD the connections between entities are largely along a national axis only. A second group are the parties involved in the projects being realized within the TA activities: these are practitioners who have actively collaborated with the Co-UDlabs partners and hence have an accurate picture on the benefits of collaborating and sharing knowledge with academic institutes. This group may also act as ‘ambassadors’ for bridging the gap between practitioners and scientific institutes.

5) Unique Value proposition

*Why are you different and worth buying? Explain the **uniqueness** of your solution. Provide facts and data, explaining the performance of your product compared to alternative solutions (efficiency increase of 20%, decreased energy consumption of 10%, 30% fewer development costs, etc.).*

The uniqueness of the training content developed withing Co-UDlabs is found in:

- There is no commercial interest as the use of materials is free, or accessible a minimal cost, the underlying documents are in majority open access
- The knowledge shared is developed by independent institutes, having no conflict of interest regarding use or application.
- The content was reviewed during the Co-UDlabs project

6) Solutions

Top 3 features of your solution and how it differentiates you from competitors.

Be sure to explain the format of your solution (is it a machine, equipment, software, service, process, etc.), what it does, and how it does it.

The content of webinars, workshops and results of JRA and TA projects are well documented and (apart from some elements in the TA projects) are open access and available for a broad public. Parties can use this material in developing their own course materials and/or can be used by students for self-study purposes. In the future, e.g. on initiative of UDRAIN, materials can be updated, added or form the basis of joint course materials between universities.

7) Unfair Advantage

What is it that gives you an advantage in front of the competition? Something that can't be easily copied or bought.

This could be IPR, being first movers on new technology that takes years to develop etc. Be sure to explain why the listed points provide you with an advantage.

As far as the author can see there is hardly any unfair advantage, apart from maybe commercial parties developing course materials related to Urban Drainage overlapping with the materials developed in Co-UDlabs, on the other hand: such parties are free to use the Co-UDlabs results.

8) Channels

How will you reach your customers/early adopters?

How do you deliver/promote value?

The results from webinars etc. organized in the Co-UDlabs project are available on a YouTube channel (<https://www.youtube.com/@coudlabs3583>), this channel can be used as a means for communicating on the content of the project.

As the parties involved in Co-UDlabs have successfully taken the initiative to start a Working Group under the umbrella of the JC on Urban Drainage of the IWA/IAHR this WG will be the core of an active community on joint research activities and related training activities. The IWA/IAHR JCUD issue newsletters on a regular basis and is open access. A main concern however is the reach-out to practitioners, as all materials are formulated in English. This, however seems to be a problem that can be solved effectively in the near future as AI development in translation is making a rapid progress. Another yet unsolved problem is to how to encourage practitioners to approach scientists, some conferences (e.g. NOVATECH) aim to address this problem, possibly these conferences can be used as a channel to issue propaganda for Co-UDlabs results. Apart from these international entities, on a national level branche organizations can be utilized for communicating between science and practice.

9) Key Metrics

Key aspects/activities you need to measure to track the success (e.g. units sold, users registered, retaining users, paying customers, number of complaints ...)

Some simple metrics would be:

1/number of views on YouTube

2/number of applicants for activities issues by the JCUD WG UDRAIN

3/materials developed in Co-UDlabs used in advanced courses (e.g. in the IWA/IAHR series of European Junior Scientist Workshop (for now an EJSW is planned for October 2025 on Asset Management, in which Co-UDlabs results will be used, and for May 2026 the 6th version of the EJSW on Metrology is foreseen, also issuing Co-UDlabs results)).

10) Revenue Streams

Which will be the main revenue stream when the solution is ready for the market. Explain how each of them will generate revenue and how much you expect to generate from each stream.

Estimate revenues for seed stage after 6 months and after 3 years. Quantify amounts and prices by detailing, for example, the expected number of services provided and paid, number of licenses sold at which prices etc.

As this not a real product, but merely a means to enhance the quality of teaching materials and increasing the efficiency of educational process, no revenues are foreseen. The main philosophy is to share results and come to e.g. creation of joint curricula on UD, while making sure practitioners are enabled to update their knowledge and get into contact with academia.

11) Cost structure

Which will be the main costs when the solution is ready for the market

Prototyping, HR costs, Eng. costs, MFG costs, marketing costs etc.

Estimate costs for each "cost-entity". Estimate costs after seed stage 6 months and 3 years.

Basically, all costs involved have to be raised by parties using materials, the materials themselves are free.

KER9 – Camera system to track flow velocities, depths and other features

1) Problem

Top 3 problems

Explain: **What** is the problem and **why** is it a problem.

Additionally, attempt to add numbers or quantifiable measures that will clearly highlight the scale of the problem.

Urban drainage systems are essential for managing stormwater and wastewater, safeguarding public health, and reducing the risk of flooding in urban areas. However, these systems are becoming increasingly strained by challenges such as urban growth, climate change, and the degradation of aging infrastructure. At the European level, the new Urban Wastewater Treatment Directive (UWWTD) will require the development of new stormwater management plans and the implementation of extensive monitoring across drainage systems. Although some wastewater operators are already monitoring their networks, upcoming legal requirements will significantly increase the scope and intensity of monitoring activities. For instance, the directive will require continuous monitoring of Combined Sewer Overflows (CSOs), whereas currently only a small fraction of these discharge points are monitored. In Spain alone, there are over 30,000 CSO discharge points, of which less than 20% are currently being monitored. Across the EU, the total number of CSO discharge points likely exceeds 250,000. Ensuring the efficiency and resilience of urban drainage systems requires a shift toward continuous, data-driven monitoring and proactive management strategies. The three primary challenges are:

- **Difficult measurement environments:** Sewers and urban drainage systems present challenging conditions for measurement. Current sensors for monitoring velocities and water levels are expensive, require frequent maintenance, and have high associated costs.
- **Lack of comprehensive monitoring strategies:** Developing a complete and continuous monitoring approach to support proactive management in urban drainage networks is complicated by installation constraints and system complexity.
- **Monitoring for blockages and spills:** No commercial sensors currently exist to continuously monitor illegal discharges, fats, and other floating debris that can accumulate in sewers, causing blockages and increasing the risk of flooding.

The investment costs for monitoring a typical section of a sewer network range between €15,000 and €90,000, depending on the parameters measured and the complexity of the installation. The proposed camera system offers a cost-effective alternative, being competitive with the installation of a conventional flowmeter, which can be 5 to 10 times more expensive. Furthermore, maintenance costs are expected to be significantly lower, as the system is contactless and non-intrusive, reducing wear and the need for frequent servicing. In some situations, the system could also serve as a proxy for water quality indicators, enabling broader applications beyond hydraulic monitoring.

2) Existing alternatives to address the same problems

Indicate how these problems are solved today.

Traditional monitoring methods rely heavily on single-point sensors and periodic manual inspections, which, while informative, often lack the spatial and temporal resolution needed for comprehensive system oversight. These methods also face limitations in scalability and maintenance, particularly with intrusive sensor technologies. Only one Swiss SME's is known giving this kind of services for river monitoring, but the application of the technology to urban drainage systems is not straightforward and expertise is needed to fully exploit the data obtained.

3) Customer segment

Identify who has the problem, define target customers. Distinguish between users and customers (customers buy, users "use")

Be clear on explaining the geographic location of your customers, the industry in which they are operating in, as well as connecting them with the problem in question.

Target customers are water utilities, research institutions and SMEs working on urban drainage field that will be favored with cutting-edge software and hardware to be applied to a wide type of urban drainage systems. Also, the open platform to be developed will serve as a basis for new applications by scientists and developers.

4) Early adopters

Who are they? What is your relation to them? etc.

Explain the geographic location, connect them to the problem, explain exactly why these will be the first adopters, clarify your current connection to them etc.

The initial adopters of our system will be stakeholders in the national markets of the countries of the partners involved in its development (Spain and The Netherlands), as well as practitioners within the Co-UDlabs community. These stakeholders include public and private entities responsible for urban drainage and sewer networks, who are increasingly interested in advanced monitoring solutions to enhance the efficiency and sustainability of their operations. Current connection to these stakeholders through project partnerships and the Co-UDlabs community ensures a strong foundation for collaboration and trust, making them ideal first adopters. Beyond the hardware, the system could be complemented with advanced consulting services, offering a comprehensive package tailored to their needs and further reinforcing its appeal.

5) Unique Value proposition

*Why are you different and worth buying? Explain the **uniqueness** of your solution.*

Provide facts and data, explaining the performance of your product compared to alternative solutions (efficiency increase of 20%, decreased energy consumption of 10%, 30% fewer development costs, etc.).

Advancements in optical monitoring have opened new possibilities for urban drainage management. Local camera systems equipped with automated image-processing algorithms can now measure critical variables, including flow velocity, water levels, and structural conditions, with greater precision and efficiency. These innovations have been applied in other fields such as river monitoring or laboratory experiments, but not in real urban drainage systems, which implies specific challenges to overcome and knowledge of the processes involved. These innovations have been made possible by the increasing availability of cost-effective hardware, the rise of open-source computer vision tools, and significant progress in AI-driven image analysis. Moreover, these systems offer substantial cost-saving benefits. Operational costs can be reduced by over 50% as the need for frequent field visits to clean and maintain sensors is minimized. Additionally, installation costs are significantly lower, as a single camera system can simultaneously measure flow and water levels, eliminating the need for multiple sensors. As these technologies continue to evolve, they provide promising solutions for addressing the growing demands and challenges of urban drainage systems.

6) Solutions

Top 3 features of your solution and how it differentiates you from competitors.

Be sure to explain the format of your solution (is it a machine, equipment, software, service, process, etc.), what it does, and how it does it.

The solution consists of an edge computing system on RaspberryPi (or similar equipment) to track flow velocities and depths in UDS. The solution offers hardware and open software. *The three features that make the camera system different from other solutions are:*

- Non-intrusive low-maintenance sensor.
- A scalable and flexible solution applicable to sewers and other urban drainage systems. The low-cost hardware and automated image-processing algorithms give the sensors the potential as data source for distributed monitoring networks.
- The system is based on rapidly evolving technologies, which allows for its potential adaptation to new needs and challenges such as continuously monitoring of floating debris and spills.

7) Unfair Advantage

What is it that gives you an advantage in front of the competition? Something that can't be easily copied or bought.

This could be IPR, being first movers on new technology that takes years to develop etc. Be sure to explain why the listed points provide you with an advantage.

Our system to measure velocities offers a unique advantage by providing comprehensive monitoring capabilities, capturing velocity fields rather than just point or profile measurements. Its non-intrusive design ensures reliability in aggressive environments, avoiding common issues like blockages and equipment failures. The use of affordable hardware makes it cost-effective and scalable, allowing for extensive urban system monitoring that is often impractical with traditional devices. Furthermore, the system is designed to adapt to advancements in AI and vision technologies, ensuring it remains relevant and future-ready. By complementing existing equipment and leveraging AI-driven analytics, it enables seamless integration and coordination across control sections or entire networks, providing a robust and innovative solution that is difficult to replicate. Only one Swiss SME's is known giving this kind of services for river monitoring, but the application of the technology to urban drainage systems is not straightforward and expertise is needed to give a complete service.

8) Channels

*How will you reach your customers/early adopters?
How do you deliver/promote value?*

Early adopters and customers will be engaged through established collaborations with the partners involved and within the Co-UDlabs project environment, which serves as an ideal platform for this purpose by connecting a wide network of stakeholders in the urban drainage field. Initial outreach will focus on consolidated relationships with national water utilities. The Universidade da Coruña (UDC), for instance, has led and participated in multiple projects with utilities across Spain — including in Barcelona, Madrid, and Seville — and actively contributes to sectoral networks such as the Jornadas de Ingeniería del Agua and the Asociación Española de Abastecimientos de Agua y Saneamiento (AEAS). In parallel, Deltares maintains ongoing collaborations with Dutch water utilities and SMEs, several of which have already shown interest in the proposed solution. Furthermore, the extensive network developed through Co-UDlabs represents a unique opportunity to reach out to potential customers and users across Europe, fostering early engagement and feedback from a representative group of end-users.

9) Key Metrics

Key aspects/activities you need to measure to track the success (e.g. units sold, users registered, retaining users, paying customers, number of complaints ...)

The key metrics for tracking the success of the system are i) ongoing projects and collaboration and ii) installed units.

10) Revenue Streams

Which will be the main revenue stream when the solution is ready for the market. Explain how each of them will generate revenue and how much you expect to generate from each stream.

Estimate revenues for seed stage after 6 months and after 3 years. Quantify amounts and prices by detailing, for example, the expected number of services provided and paid, number of licenses sold at which prices etc.

Main expected revenue would be collaboration projects with stakeholders. With the experience of a similar project that UDC is currently developed, the revenues could be estimated as:

- After 6 months: 100,000 €. Number of ongoing services: 2, Installed cameras: 3
- After 3 years: 800,000€. Number of ongoing services: 5, Installed cameras: 12

11) Cost structure

*Which will be the main costs when the solution is ready for the market
Prototyping, HR costs, Eng. costs, MFG costs, marketing costs etc.*

Estimate costs for each "cost-entity". Estimate costs after seed stage 6 months and 3 years.

The main costs are primarily associated with the highly skilled labor required to design the necessary adapted solutions, prepare the equipment, and provide guidance or directly handle data processing. Additionally, significant resources will be allocated to the ongoing development of the software to enhance the quality of the service offered. These areas with the supervision of the tasks by senior scientist represent the core of the investment required to ensure the solution's effectiveness and competitiveness in the market. Costs for

production, installation and maintenance of the equipment are also included. Once the equipment is ready for commercialization, the main costs are estimated as follows:

- Production. This part includes the purchase of the hardware components and storage and communication systems that make up the equipment. It also includes the hours spent assembling the components, and configuring the software and data transfer module.
- Installation. This part includes the purchase of elements to install the system in the points required, and also the costs associated with travelling to visit the emplacements and make the installation.
- Maintenance service. Maintenance of the installed equipment and technical assistance.
- Human resources. This part includes the costs of setting up a spin-off or start-up, corporate taxes, salaries.
- Marketing. Visits to customers, attendance at forums and conferences

The costs after the 6-month and 3-year seed phase would be as follows:

6 months:

- Production costs: 1200 € per unit. Total: 3,600 €
- Installation costs: 3000 € for each service. Total: 6,000 €
- Maintenance service: 2,000 € for each service. Total: 4,000 €
- Human resources: 40,000 €.
- Marketing: 5,000 €.

Total: 62,600 €.

3 years:

- Production costs: 1200 € per unit. Total: 8,400 €
- Installation costs: 3000 € for each service. Total: 15,000 €
- Maintenance service: 2,000 € for each service. Total: 10,000 €
- Human resources: 280,000 €
- Marketing: 25,000 €

Total: 338,400 €.

KER10 – MONTSE: MONitoring Temperatures in SEDiments

1) Problem

Top 3 problems

Explain: **What** is the problem and **why** is it a problem.

Additionally, attempt to add numbers or quantifiable measures that will clearly highlight the scale of the problem.

MONTSE addresses the sediment accumulation in urban drainage systems. These infrastructures lose their hydraulic or solids retention capacity due to the presence of large amounts of sediments that, in most cases, accumulate gradually over time. The MONTSE system has been designed with the aim of monitoring the accumulation processes and, consequently, optimising the maintenance and cleaning strategies of some urban drainage assets to ensure optimum operation and minimize obstructions and overflow episodes.

2) Existing alternatives to address the same problems

Indicate how these problems are solved today.

At present, there is a lack of technology capable of continuously and remotely measuring sediment accumulation processes in drainage infrastructures. Previous developments have largely consisted of equipment with high installation and maintenance costs, which is difficult to scale in urban drainage networks. In most locations, maintenance and cleaning operations are carried out based on previous experience, but without any knowledge of the current state of each infrastructure. In some cases, CCTV vehicles are used periodically, but their use is focused on inspections rather than measuring sediment accumulation.

3) Customer segment

Identify who has the problem, define target customers. Distinguish between users and customers (customers buy, users “use”)

Be clear on explaining the geographic location of your customers, the industry in which they are operating in, as well as connecting them to the problem in question.

The users of this system are the local or regional water management companies and authorities, which in many cases will be the same as the customers, except where they have outsourced or concessioned management services to service companies or consultancies. In some cases, it will be public companies that manage local or regional water supply and sewer services, while private companies that operate these services may do so in more than one geographical location. In both scenarios, the companies want to ensure the proper functioning of the drainage infrastructure for which they are responsible for cleaning and maintenance. Also, MONTSE system will serve as a basis for new applications by scientists and developers.

4) Early adopters

Who are they? What is your relation to them? etc.

Explain the geographic location, connect them to the problem, explain exactly why these will be the first adopters, clarify your current connection to them etc.

Early adopters of this technology may be urban water management companies directly. The MONTSE system has been developed and validated by several project partners (mainly UDC, Eawag, Deltares and UoS), thus creating strong links and collaborations with local companies and authorities interested in its application in real environments and its development to commercial level. Furthermore, at the research level, the technology is applicable to the development and improvement of sediment transport models in urban drainage systems. Therefore, other possible early adopters could be the research centres themselves through knowledge development projects.

5) Unique Value proposition

Why are you different and worth buying? Explain the **uniqueness** of your solution.

Provide facts and data, explaining the performance of your product compared to alternative solutions (efficiency increase of 20%, decreased energy consumption of 10%, 30% fewer development costs, etc.).

MONTSE is a technology that allows continuous monitoring of sediment accumulation with an accuracy in estimating sediment depths of less than 1 cm. It uses low-cost temperature sensors as an estimation tool, which makes this solution scalable in an urban area. The rest of the components used are also standard, as well as the data transfer protocols. This reduces installation and maintenance costs compared to other alternatives developed or under development, such as sonar sensors, optical or acoustic sensors, or manual measurements during periodic visits to the infrastructure. The savings in production, installation and maintenance costs compared to other technologies are in the order of thousands of Euros, while the savings in periodic visits are estimated to be in the order of hundreds of Euros. In addition, this technology ensures the optimization of cleaning processes, whose price varies according to the location and, at the same time, guarantees an efficient performance of the network, avoiding episodes of overflow and the associated costs.

6) Solutions

Top 3 features of your solution and how it differentiates you from competitors.

Be sure to explain the format of your solution (is it a machine, equipment, software, service, process, etc.), what it does, and how it does it.

The three features that make MONTSE different from other solutions are:

- On-line monitoring of sediment accumulation.
- Use of temperature sensors, the cost of which is relatively lower than other alternatives.
- Scalable solution applicable to various drainage systems.

7) Unfair Advantage

What is it that gives you an advantage in front of the competition? Something that can't be easily copied or bought.

This could be IPR, being first movers on new technology that takes years to develop etc. Be sure to explain why the listed points provide you with an advantage.

Although there are other devices based on temperature sensors, the main advantages of MONTSE are its application to the estimation of sediment accumulation and, moreover, its use to urban drainage systems. An innovative methodology has been developed which establishes a relationship between thermal variations and depths of accumulated sediments. Alternatively, it could be simplified to determine whether the sediments have exceeded the depth thresholds that compromise the efficiency of the system. In addition, the intellectual property of the MONTSE system can be protected by a utility model or a patent.

8) Channels

How will you reach your customers/early adopters? How do you deliver/promote value?

Early adopters and customers would be reached through existing collaborations. The Co-UDlabs project presents itself as an ideal platform for this purpose because many companies, research centres and authorities are involved in the project. Attendance at forums and conferences also plays an important role in promoting the MONTSE system by showing the results obtained during the development phase.

9) Key Metrics

Key aspects/activities you need to measure to track the success (e.g. units sold, users registered, retaining users, paying customers, number of complaints ...)

The key metrics for tracking the success of the system are i) installed units and ii) ongoing projects where a monitoring service for sediment accumulation in drainage systems is being provided.

10) Revenue Streams

Which will be the main revenue streams when the solution is ready for the market. Explain how each of them will generate revenue and how much you expect to generate from each stream.

Estimate revenues for seed stage after 6 months and after 3 years. Quantify amounts and prices by detailing, for example, the expected number of services provided and paid, number of licenses sold at which prices etc.

Initially, the main revenue would be obtained through the provision of services to companies in charge of managing the water supply and sewer assets. The service would consist, besides the configuration and installation of equipment, of monitoring sediment accumulation to establish cleaning protocols to ensure the optimal functioning of drainage infrastructure. In addition, it would be possible to count on income from financing programmes to promote technology-based small and medium-sized enterprises during the initial phase.

Estimated income at six months:

- Number of services provided (not completed): 3.
- Number of equipment installed in operation: 36.
- Total revenue in 6 months: 75,000 €.

Estimated income at three years:

- Number of services provided (not completed): 10.
- Number of equipment installed in operation: 150.
- Total revenue in 6 months: 400,000 €.

11) Cost structure

Which will be the main costs when the solution is ready for the market

Prototyping, HR costs, Eng. costs, MFG costs, marketing costs etc.

Estimate costs for each "cost-entity". Estimate costs after seed stage 6 months and 3 years.

Depending on the level of detail of the build-up estimates, the costs may vary significantly. Once the equipment is ready for commercialisation, the main costs will be as follows:

- Production. This part includes the purchase of the electronic components and sensors that make up the equipment. We are currently seeking to establish production channels to facilitate and reduce the cost of these components. It also includes the hours spent assembling the components, calibrating the sensors and configuring the data transfer module.
- Installation. This part includes the purchase of elements that facilitate the commissioning of the system, and the costs associated with travelling to make the installation (transport, accommodation, allowances).
- Maintenance service. Depending on the customer's requirements, the costs are divided between the maintenance of the installed equipment and the adjustment of the models (complex or simplified).
- Human resources. This part includes the costs of setting up a spin-off or start-up, corporate taxes, salaries.
- Marketing. Visits to customers, attendance at forums and conferences

The costs after the 6-month and 3-year seed phase would be as follows:

6 months:

- Production costs: 300 € - 400 € per unit. Total: 12,600 €
- Installation costs: 500 € for each device. Total: 18,000 €.
- Maintenance service: 800 €.
- Human resources: 30,000 €.
- Marketing: 4,000 €.

3 years:

- Production costs: 150 € - 200 € per unit. Total: 26,000 €
- Installation costs: 500 € for each device. Total: 75,000 €.
- Maintenance service: 5,000 €
- Human resources: 240,000 €
- Marketing: 8,000 €